
OSMOSE Documentation

Nicolas Barrier

Philippe Verley

Bruno Ernande

Arnaud Grüss

Alaia Morell

Ricardo Oliveros-Ramos

Hanna Schenk

Morgane Travers-Trolet

Laure Velez

Yunne-Jai Shin

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The present document contains all the necessary information and guidelines to help understand the principles and assumptions of the OSMOSE model, apply it to a specific case study and run simulations for addressing specific issues. The OSMOSE model aims at exploring fish community dynamics and the ecosystem effects of fishing and climate change. It is an Individual-based model (IBM) which focuses on fish species and their trophic interactions ([Shin and Cury, 2001, Shin and Cury, 2004]).

The Osmose model assumes opportunistic predation based on spatial co-occurrence and size adequacy between a predator and its prey (size-based opportunistic predation). It represents fish individuals grouped in schools, which are characterized by their size, weight, age, taxonomy and geographical location (2D model), and which undergo different processes of fish life cycle (growth, explicit predation, natural and starvation mortalities, reproduction and migration) and a fishing mortality distinct for each species and structured by age/size, space and season. The model needs basic biological parameters for growth and reproduction processes, that are often available for a wide range of species, and which can be found in FishBase for instance. It also needs to be forced by spatial distribution maps for each species, by age/size/stage and by season depending on data availability. In output, a variety of size-based and species-based ecological indicators can be produced and compared to in situ data (surveys and catch data) at different levels of aggregation: at the species level (e.g. mean size, mean size-at-age, maximum size, mean trophic level, within-species distribution of TL), and at the community level (e.g. slope and intercept of size spectrum, Shannon diversity index, mean TL of catch). The model can be fitted to observed biomass and catch data, using a dedicated evolutionary algorithm. Recent developments have focused on the coupling of OSMOSE to various hydrodynamic and biogeochemical models, allowing to build end-to-end models of marine ecosystems that explicit combined effects of climate and fishing on fish dynamics.

ODD DESCRIPTION

The present section contains all the necessary information and guidelines to help understand the principles and assumptions of the OSMOSE model, apply it to a specific case study and run simulations for addressing specific issues. The OSMOSE model aims at exploring fish community dynamics and the ecosystem effects of fishing and climate change. It is an Individual-based model (IBM) which focuses on fish species and their trophic interactions ([Shin and Cury, 2001, Shin and Cury, 2004]).

The model description in this section follows the ODD (“Overview”, “Design concept” and “Details”) protocol for describing individual- or agent-based models ([Grimm *et al.*, 2010, Grimm *et al.*, 2020]).

1.1 Purpose and patterns

1.1.1 Purpose

The OSMOSE model represents the dynamics of fish communities. It is a multispecies and spatial model which lies on size-based predation, traits-based life history, and individual-based processes. The model aims to explore the functioning of marine ecosystems, the ecosystem effects of fishing and climate changes, the impacts of management measures (changes in fishing pressure and fishing strategies, implementation of marine protected areas).

The OSMOSE model represents the ecosystem dynamics of fish communities in marine ecosystems. It is an individual-based, spatially-explicit multispecies model accounting for explicit trophic interactions. The main characteristics of the model are opportunistic predation based on size and spatial co-occurrence of predators and preys

The aim of the model is to explore the functioning of marine trophic webs, notably in response to perturbations such as fishing or climate change.

1.1.2 Patterns

The model is evaluated by comparing the model outputs with observations of the marine ecosystem. These observations generally include catches, catches at length, biomass, abundance for different species.

1.2 Entities, state variables, and scales

1.2.1 Entities

In the current section, the different types of entities of the Osmose model are described.

- The `Configuration` entity describes the parameters and entities that will be shared among the different simulations.
- The `Simulation` entity describes a given simulation. Simulations differ from each other if stochasticity is enabled.
- The `Cell` entity describes the individual cells of the Osmose computation 2D grid (longitude, latitude, cell index, etc.)
- The `Species` entity represents the species whose life-cycle is fully represented. This entity contain **fixed** parameters, which are not modified during the simulation.
- The `BackgroundSpecies` entity represents the species whose life-cycle is not represented. These species can feed on and be eaten by `Species`, and can be fished. This entity contain **fixed** parameters, which are not modified during the simulation.
- The `ResourceSpecies` entity represents the low-trophic level species. These species cannot predate `Species` or `BackgroundSpecies` but can be eaten by them. This entity contain **fixed** parameters, which are not modified during the simulation.
- The `School` entity describes a group of `Species` individuals, whose life cycle is fully considered and which all share the same characteristics (age, weight, species, location, etc, trophic level).
- The `BackgroundSchool` entity describes a group of `BackgroundSpecies` individuals, whose biomass is provided as input and whose life-cycle is not simulated and which all share the same characteristics (age, weight, species, location, etc, trophic level).
- The `Resource` entity describes a swarm of `ResourceSpecies`, whose biomass is provided as input.

1.2.2 State variables

Simulation

The `Simulation` entity contains the following state variables:

Table 1.1: Simulation state variables

Variable	Description	Type	Units
<code>i_step_simu</code>	Times step of the simulation	<code>int</code> , $\in [0, N_{year} \times N_{step_year}]$	
<code>rank</code>	Index of the simulation	<code>int</code> , $\in [0, N_{simulation}]$	
<code>schoolSet</code>	List of the <code>School</code> inside the simulation	<code>SchoolSet</code>	
<code>backSchoolSet</code>	List of the <code>BackgroundSchool</code> inside the simulation	<code>BackgroundSchoolSet</code>	

Cell

The Cell entity contains the following state variables:

Table 1.2: Cell state variables

Variable	Description	Type	Units
i	i-index of the current cell on the 2D grid	int, $\in [0, N_x - 1]$	
j	j-index of the current cell on the 2D grid	int, $\in [0, N_y - 1]$	
land	true if the cell is on land	boolean	
lat	latitude	float	Degrees North
lon	longitude	float	Degrees East
surf	surface	float, > 0	m^2

Species

The Species entities contain the following state variables:

Table 1.3: Species state variables

Variable	Description	Type	Units
name	name of the species	string	
index	index of the species	int, $\in [0, N_{species} - 1]$	
fileIndex	index of the species in the configuration file	int, > 0	
lifespan	species life span	int, > 0	time-steps
c	allometric factor	float	
bPower	allometric power	float	
sizeMaturity	Size at maturity	float	cm
ageMaturity	Age at maturity	float	year
eggSize	Size of eggs	float	cm
eggWeight	Weight of eggs	float	g
firstFeedingAgeDt	First feeding age	int	time-step
larvaeToAdultsAgeDt	Age at which the school is considered as adult	int	time-step
TL_EGG	egg trophic level	float, = 3.0	

The BackgroundSpecies entities contain the following state variables:

Table 1.4: BackgroundSpecies state variables

Variable	Description	Type	Units
name	Species name	string	
index	Species index.	int, $\in [N_{species}, N_{species} + N_{bkg\ species}] - 1$	
fileindex	index of the species in the	int, > 0	
age	Age array	[float]	years
ageDt	Age array	[int]	time-step
c	allometric factor	float	
bPower	allometric power	float float	
classProportion	Proportion of biomass attributed to each size-class	float[]	%
length	Length array	float[]	cm
nClass	Number of size-classes	int, > 1	
trophicLevel	Array of trophic level	float[]	
timeSeries	Time series of proportion of biomass attributed to each size-class		

Table 1.5: ResourceSpecies state variables

Variable	Description	Units
accessMax	Maximum value for resource accessibility	0.99
accessibilityCoeff	Fraction of the resource biomass available to the fish	[0, 1]
fileindex	Species index in the configuration file	
index	Resource species index	
name	Resource species name	
sizeMax	Maximum size of the plankton size	Cm
sizeMin	Maximum size of the plankton size	Cm
trophicLevel	Trophic level	

School

The School entity contains the following state variables:

Table 1.6: School state variables

Variable	Description	Type	Units
abundance	Number of fish in the school at the beginning of the time-step	float	
biomass	Biomass of the school at the beginning of the school	float	Tons
instantaneous-Abundance	Instantaneous number of fish in the school	float	
instantaneous-Biomass	Instantaneous biomass of the school at the beginning of the school	float	Tons
discarded-Biomass	Biomass of the school that has been discarded by each fishing gear	float[]	Tons
fishedBiomass	Biomass of the school that has been landed by each fishing gear	float[]	Tons
nDead	Number of dead fish in the current time nstep for each mortality cause (predation, fishing, natural mortality, starvation)	float	
predSuccess-Rate	Predation success rate	float	%
preyed-Biomass	Biomass of prey ingested by the school at current time step	float	Tons
preys	List of preys eaten by the school	HashMap<Integer>	Prey
uuid	Unique identifier of the individual	UUID	
lat	Latitude of the individual	float	Degrees north
lon	Longitude of the individual	float	Degrees east
x	i-index of the individual in the 2D grid	int	
y	j-index of the individual in the 2D grid	int	
ageDt	Age of the school	int	Time-step
eggRetained	Buffer variable that will temporarily retain some eggs inside a time step	float	
length	Length of the individuals in the school	float	cm
lengthi	Length of the individuals in the school at the beginning of the time-step	float	cm
out	True if the school is out of the computation domain	boolean	
starvationRate	Starvation rate of the school	float	
trophicLevel	Trophic level of the school	float	
weight	Weight of the school	float	tons
species	School species	Species	
abundance-HasChanged	True if abundance has changed in the current time-step	boolean	
accessibility	Array of accessibility of the school to its preys	float[]	
ageDeath	Age at which a school individuals die times the abundance	float[]	$N \times$ <i>years</i>

Table 1.7: BackgroundSchool state variables

Variable	Description	Units
abundance	Number of fish in the school at the beginning of the time-step	
biomass	Biomass of the school at the beginning of the school	Tons
discarded-Biomass	Biomass of the school that has been discarded by each fishing gear	Tons
fished-Biomass	Biomass of the school that has been landed by each fishing gear	Tons
nDead	Number of dead fish in the current time nstep for each mortality cause (predation, fishing, natural mortality, starvation)	
predSuccess-Rate	Predation success rate	%
preyed-Biomass	Biomass of prey ingested by the school at current time step	Tons
preys	List of preys eaten by the school	
uuid	Unique identifier of the individual	
lat	Latitude of the individual	
lon	Longitude of the individual	
x	i-index of the individual in the 2D grid	
y	j-index of the individual in the 2D grid	
classIndex	Class index to which belongs the school	
bkgSpecies	School background species	

1.2.3 Scales

The basic units of OSMOSE are fish schools, which are composed of individuals that belong to the same species, and that have the same age, size (length, weight), food requirements and, at a given time step, the same geographical coordinates. From the school states (hereafter called individual states), biomass and abundance can be tracked at the population or community levels along with the size, age, and spatial dimensions.

Other variables can be reported such as the trophic level, the diets, the different sources of mortality, the catches from fishing operations. Because each school simulated in OSMOSE is represented from the egg stage to the terminal age, which necessitates high calculation and memory capacities, and because comprehensive information on entire life cycles needs to be parameterized, the selection of focus species is made parsimoniously, and usually between 10 and 20 high-trophic level species or functional groups are explicitly considered in OSMOSE applications.

The model operates on a weekly to monthly time step, and runs up to 100 years or more depending on applications and simulations.

For eggs (age 0), weight and sizes are provided as parameters. For the others, conversion from size to weight (and conversely) is obtained by using allometric relationships:

$$W = c \times L^b$$

$$L = \left(\frac{W}{c}\right)^{\frac{1}{b}}$$

where the c parameter is a condition factor, and b the allometric power.

Biomass to abundance conversion for a school is made by using the mean weight of the school:

$$B = N \times W$$

$$N = \frac{B}{W}$$

Table 1.8: Allometric parameters

species.length2weight.condition.factor.sp#	Allometric factor (c)
species.length2weight.allometric.power.sp#	Allometric power (b)
species.egg.size.sp#	Egg size (cm)
species.egg.weight.sp#	Egg weight (g)

1.3 Process overview and scheduling

The life cycle of each focus species included in the OSMOSE model is modelled, starting with the egg stage. At the first time step, eggs are produced and split into a number of super-individuals called schools. At each time step, OSMOSE simulates the main life history processes for these schools, starting with the release of fish schools within their distribution area which is specified in input for each species and by age when presence/absence data are available. Then different sources of mortality are applied including predation, fishing, starvation and other natural mortality. In OSMOSE, predation is assumed to be opportunistic and based on predator and prey size adequation and spatio-temporal co-occurrence. Depending on the predation success, somatic growth is then implemented and mature individuals spawn at the end of the time step and produce new eggs for the next step.

1.4 Design concepts

Following the ODD framework and terminology, we briefly present here some design concepts characterizing OSMOSE.

1.4.1 Basic principles

Dieta data, such as those of [Shannon *et al.*, 2003], suggest that patterns in fish diets include variability in time and space and prey switching, cannibalism and omnivory. Therefore, two species can be a predator or prey of one another depending on the life stages considered. Therefore, predation in Osmose is size-based, taking into account thresholds for predator/prey size ratio, and relies on the spatio-temporal co-occurrence of individuals.

1.4.2 Emergence

From the local interactions, population and community dynamics emerge. In particular, the whole food web structure emerges from size-based local predation interactions.

1.4.3 Adaptation

Adaptation is not implemented in Osmose.

Fig. 1.1: Scheduling of the different Osmose processes

1.4.4 Objectives

Objectives are not implemented in Osmose.

1.4.5 Learning

Learning is not implemented in Osmose.

1.4.6 Prediction

1.4.7 Sensing

Schools are assumed to know perfectly all the potential prey which are located in its vicinity, i.e. in the same cell of the grid. They also know the limits of their habitat.

1.4.8 Interaction

Super-individuals/schools interact locally through predation events.

1.4.9 Stochasticity

There are different sources of stochasticity in the model. First, the order at which schools act and interact. There is a randomization of the precedence of schools crossed with a randomization of different sources of mortality (predation, fishing, other natural mortality). In addition, fish movements are also randomized within their habitats.

1.4.10 Collectives

As the total number of fish (from eggs to adult fish) to be taken into account in the simulated system can reach a value of the order of 10^{12} , the model was not brought down to the fish level but to an aggregated level consisting of a group of fish having similar ecological attributes. The unit of action and interaction, i.e., the “super-individual” as defined by [Scheffer *et al.*, 1995], is a group of fish having the same size, the same spatial coordinates, requiring similar food, and belonging to the same species (therefore having similar physiological and morphological characteristics). For convenience, this super-individual is also called a “fish school” in the following sections.

1.4.11 Observation

For model testing and fitting, a variety of auxiliary state variables can be used in output of the model and compared with observations, data time series, and maps. Typically, species biomass and commercial catches, age or size distribution of abundance/biomass, diets can be confronted to observations.

1.5 Initialization

In Osmose, there are several initialisation methods.

1.5.1 Seeding method

In the seeding method, the system starts from a pristine state, with no schools in the domain. For a few years (user-defined), Osmose will release some eggs for every species. The eggs enter the different steps of the life cycle, and once the fish reach sexual maturity, the reproduction process takes over and Osmose stops the seeding, unless the spawning stock biomass gets depleted. In that case Osmose resumes the seeding by releasing some eggs until there are again mature individuals in the system for carrying on the reproduction process. Osmose completely ceases the seeding when the simulation reaches the maximal number of years for seeding (user-defined).

By following this approach:

- No assumption is made about the structure of the populations but it emerges from individual interactions
- it reduces computing requirements for the spin-up as the first years are the fastest to run
- it reduces the number of time steps for the spin-up
- it minimizes the amplitude of population oscillations

The initialisation process is controlled by two parameters:

- `population.seeding.year.max` defines the number of years for running the seeding process (from year 0 to `population.seeding.year.max`), and during which Osmose ensures that some eggs will be released even though there are no mature individuals in the system. Then, the seeding ceases completely until the end of the simulation. If the parameter is not specified, Osmose will set it by default to the lifespan of the longest lived species of the system.
- `population.seeding.biomass.sp#` defines the spawning stock biomass (SSB) that Osmose considers during the seeding period when there are no mature adults to ensure the reproduction process. SSB is then used to compute the number of eggs to be released in the system (cf. [Section 1.7.7](#)).

1.5.2 Using a NetCDF file

Another possibility to initialize the Osmose model is by using a NetCDF file. This method is used if the `simulation.restart.file` or the `population.initialization.file` are set.

These parameters point to the NetCDF file that will be used to restart the simulation. If `simulation.restart.file` is used, then one file per replicate is expected (suffix ends with `.nc.#`, with `#` the index of the simulation).

1.5.3 Using relative biomass

Another method to initialize Osmose is to use relative biomass. This method is called if the `population.initialization.relativebiomass.enabled` is enabled. With this method, the user specifies, for each species:

- `population.initialization.biomass.sp#`: the initialization biomass for each species (B_s , float)
- `population.initialization.size.sp#`: the size-boundaries (float[]). Size is $N_{class} + 1$
- `population.initialization.tl.sp#`: the trophic levels for each size-class (float[], size N_{class})
- `population.initialization.relativebiomass.sp#`: the proportion of total biomass to attribute to each size-class ($P_{s,k}$, float[], size N_{class} , $\in [0, 1]$)
- `population.initialization.age.sp#`: the age to attribute to each size-class (float[], size N_{class})

- `population.initialization.nschool.sp#`: the number of schools to create for each size-class ($N_{s,k}$)

Using all these parameters, schools for a given species are initialized as follows.

- For each size-class, computes the biomass to release by multiplying input biomass and relative proportion:
 $B_{s,k} = B_s \times P_{s,k}$.
- Loop over the number of schools to create
- Randomly select a length between the lower and upper size-bonds of the given class. If age is 0, force length to be equal to species `eggSize`.
- Using length, computes the weight using allometric relationship. If age is 0, force weight to be equal to species `eggWeight`.
- Compute the number of individuals to put in school i : $A_{s,k,i} = \frac{B_{s,k} \times 10^6}{N_{s,k} \times W_{s,k,i}}$

The steps are summarized in Fig. 1.2

Fig. 1.2: Initialization steps using the relative biomass method.

1.6 Input data

1.6.1 Configuration files

An Osmose configuration file is a text based file. The name of the file does not matter, but we recommend that you avoid any special characters and space in the name of the file as it might generate IO errors when you'll be running Osmose from the command line or calibrating the model in a UNIX environment. The extension of the file does not matter either.

We call the main configuration file the file that is either listed in `Osmose filePath.txt` or given as a command line argument. The main configuration file can contain comments, blank lines and parameters. Here is how the Osmose configuration manager proceeds when it opens the main configuration file. It scans every line of the file looking for parameters. Some lines are automatically discarded:

- empty lines (regardless of blank or tab characters).
- lines that start with a punctuation character, one of `!"#$%&'()*+,-./:;<=>?@[]^_`/~`

For comments, it is recommended to start the line with `#` or `//`

A parameter is formed by the juxtaposition of three elements: **key**, **separator** and **value**.

The **key** can be any sequence of characters, without blank or any special characters (dot, hyphen and underscore are accepted). Example of keys:

```
simulation.ncpu
predation.ingestion.rate.max.sp6
```

Osmose makes no difference between upper and lower case: `simulation.ncpu`, `simulation.Ncpu`, `Simulation.nCPU`, `SIMULATION.NCPU` designate the same key.

Keys starting with `osmose.configuration.*` (the star `*` being any sequence of characters that follow the same rules than any other key) has a special meaning to the configuration manager. It means the value of this parameter is the path of an other Osmose configuration file and the parameters in this file are to be loaded in the current configuration. That way, instead of having one big configuration file with all the parameters, it is possible to split the parameters in as many files as the user wishes. This process works recursively: one file contains one or several parameters `osmose.configuration.*` that point to configuration files that may contains one or several parameters `osmose.configuration.*`, and so on. OSMOSE handles the sub-configuration file exactly the same way as it handles the main configuration file (same convention for comments, special characters and naming of). As mentioned previously, the **main configuration file** designates the file that is listed in `filePath.txt` or given to Osmose as an input argument.

The separator can be any of the following characters:

- equals =
- semicolon ;
- comma ,
- colon :
- tab \t

Parameters in the same configuration file can have different separators (though it is advisable to be consistent and use the same one). The configuration manager finds out what is the separator for each parameter. The value can be any sequence of characters (even empty). The configuration manager does not try to interpret the value when it loads the configuration files, it merely stores it in a String object. A value can be served by the configuration manager as:

- a string
- an integer

- a float
- a double
- a boolean
- an array of strings, String[]
- an array of integers, int[]
- an array of floats, float[]
- an array of doubles, double[]
- a resolved path

An array of values is a sequence of values with a separator in between: *value1 separator value2 separator value3 separator value4*. Accepted separators for an array of values are the same characters listed above. The separator for an array of values can either be the same or distinct from the separator between the key and the value. The following examples are valid entries:

```
movement.map0.season;0;1;2;3;4;5
movement.map0.season=0;1;2;3;4;5
movement.map0.season = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
movement.map0.season : 0 ; 1 ; 2;3;4;5
```

and are equivalent for the configuration manager. It can be summarize as:

```
key separator1 value1 separator2 value2 separator2 value3 separator2 value4
```

with separator1 either equal or different from separator2.

CSV input file separator

Many Osmose parameters are paths to CSV file, for instance:

```
movement.map0.file
mortality.fishing.rate.byDt.byAge.file.sp#
reproduction.season.file.sp#
```

In Osmose 3 and Osmose 3 Update 1 these CSV input files had to be semicolon separated. Since Osmose 3 Update 2, CSV input file separators can be any of the following characters:

- equals =
- semicolon ;
- comma ,
- colon :
- tab \t

Osmose will detect the separator automatically and independently for every CSV file. It means that one CSV input file may be comma separated and an other one may be tab-separated, this is perfectly fine since Osmose 3 Update 2.

Decimal separator

Osmose is quite flexible in terms of separators for the configuration files (automatically detected among = , ; : t), the CSV output files (user-defined by parameter `output.csv.separator`) and the CSV input files (automatically detected among = , ; : t). On the contrary it restricts the decimal separator to dot, and only dot.

Example given: 3.14159265 or 1.618

Any other decimal separator (COMMA for instance as in French locale) will be misunderstood and will unmistakably lead to errors. One must be careful when editing CSV input files (either parameters or time series) with tools such as spreadsheets that may automatically replace decimal separator depending on the locale settings. Future Osmose release might allow the use of specific locale but for now remember that DOT is the only accepted decimal separator.

1.6.2 Forcing data

Secondly, the modelled system is driven by prey fields which are not explicitly represented as focus species in OS-MOSE. For example, biomass fields of phytoplankton and zooplankton varying in space and time are typical input to OS-MOSE. In the different OS-MOSE applications, these prey fields were usually produced from coupled hydro-dynamic and biogeochemical (BGC) models such as ROMS-NPZD ([Travers-Trolet *et al.*, 2014]), ROMS-PISCES ([Oliveros Ramos, 2014]), NEMOMed-ECO3M ([Halouani *et al.*, 2016]) or are derived from observational data ([Fu *et al.*, 2013, Grüss *et al.*, 2015]). Benthic resources can also drive the dynamics of the system as in [Halouani *et al.*, 2016].

1.6.3 Spatial distribution files

First, the spatial dynamics of OS-MOSE focus species are driven by spatial distribution maps which can vary according to time (year, season or the age of fish). These maps are derived either from observational data (presence/absence data or density maps) or from climate niche models.

1.7 Submodels

1.7.1 Incoming flux

Some species might not do the full life cycle within the simulated domain (reproduce outside the domain for example). For such species, one way to take them into account is to include a flux of schools with user-defined age or length at specific time of the year. This is done by setting either the `flux.incoming.byDt.byAge.file.sp#` or `flux.incoming.byDt.bySize.file.sp#` parameters, which are the paths of the CSV files containing the input flux.

It provides the biomass (in tons) for the given size or age classes and must be as follows:

Table 1.9: Example of input flux by time-step and by age class

Time step / Age	0	2	3	4
0	0	500	800	0
1	0	500	800	0
2	0	400	700	0
3	0	400	700	0

The values of the class intervals (first row) are automatically scanned by Osmose. If `flux.incoming.byDt.byAge.file.sp#` is provided, the corresponding length will be computed from age classes using the growth `ageToLength`

method. Conversely, if `flux.incoming.byDt.bySize.file.sp#` is provided, the corresponding age will be computed using the `lengthToAge` method (cf. Fig. 1.3).

In the above example, there are 4 age classes: `[0 2[`, `[2 3[`, `[3 4[` and `[4 lifespan[`. Osmose will compute the incoming age at the middle of the interval (i.e. 1 year, 2.5 year, 3.5 year, etc). For the first time step, Osmose will therefore input 500 tons of 2.5 year-old school and 800 tons of 3.5 year school.

The values of the time step (leftmost column) does not matter. Osmose assumes there is one line per time step. The number of time steps in the CSV file must be a multiple of the number of time steps per year. If the time series is shorter than the duration of the simulation, Osmose will loop over it. If the time series is longer than the duration of the simulation, Osmose will ignore the exceeding steps.

The state variable that is updated is the `Simulation.schoolSet` variable, to which is added these newly created schools.

The number of schools created for each species and each size-class is controlled by the `simulation.nschool.sp#` (also used in the reproduction processes). If the abundance is less than the number of schools, one school of abundance A is created. Else, N_{school} of abundance $\frac{A}{N_{school}}$ are created (cf. Fig. 1.4).

Size-classes are handled the same way than age classes, except that the last size-class covers the `[4, Linf[` interval.

Danger: The incoming biomass should be calibrated.

1.7.2 School initialisation

The school initialisation process allows to reset some variables at the beginning of the time steps.

These variables and their value after the initialization are listed below:

Table 1.10: List of reinitialized state variables

Variable	Value
<code>out</code>	false
<code>abundance</code>	instantaneous abundance at previous time-step
<code>biomass</code>	abundance x weight
<code>lengthi</code>	length at previous time step
<code>preys</code>	empty listed
<code>preyedBiomass</code>	0
<code>predSuccessRate</code>	0
<code>nEggs</code>	0
<code>ingestion</code>	0
<code>nDead</code>	array of 0
<code>ageDeath</code>	array of 0
<code>fishedBiomass</code>	array of 0
<code>this.discardedBiomass</code>	array of 0

Fig. 1.3: Initialization of the incoming flux process

Fig. 1.4: Incoming flux process

1.7.3 Resource update

The resource update consists in updating the resource forcings by reading the proper time-steps in the input NetCDF files. This updates is done for both resource and background species.

1.7.4 Spatial distribution

At each time-step, the spatial distribution of fished is randomly changed based either based on distribution maps or based on random walk processes.

The displacement mode is defined through the `movement.distribution.method.sp#`, whose values are either `random` or `maps`.

Random distribution

For random distribution, two parameters need to be defined:

Table 1.11: Random distribution parameters

Parameter	Description
<code>move-ment.distribution.ncell.sp#</code>	Number of cells in which the species is allowed to move. If undefined, the whole domain is used.
<code>move-ment.randomwalk.range.sp#</code>	Number of adjacent cells a species can use during random walk (foraging)

At the beginning of the simulation, during the initialization process, the areas where the schools can live is initialized:

- If `ncell` is not set or is equal to the total number of ocean cells, this areas is set equal to all the ocean cells of the domain.
- Else, one cell is first randomly picked up in the whole domain, and the domain is extended from neighbours to neighbours until the number of cells reaches `ncell` (cf. [Fig. 1.5](#))

Then, at each time-step, schools are moved following a random walk method within this domain, with the range defined in the parameters. Unlocated schools are randomly put in one of the cell of the defined domain.

Map definition

Another way to define species distribution is to use distribution maps, which can generally be obtained from niche modelling.

A single map is defined as follows:

Table 1.12: Spatial distribution parameters when CSV maps are provided

Parameter	Description
movement.randomwalk.range.sp#	Number of adjacent cells a species can use during random walk (foraging)
movement.file.map#	Name of the CSV file that contains the distribution map
movement.species.map#	Name of the species associated with the map.
movement.initialAge.map#	Minimum age (in years) when to use the map.
movement.lastAge.map#	Maximum age (in years) when to use the map.
movement.initialYear.map#	Minimum simulation time (in years) when to use the map.
movement.lastYear.map#	Maximum simulation time (in years) when to use the map.
movement.years.map#	Array of years during when to use the map. (instead of setting initial and final year)
movement.steps.map#	Array of time-steps during when to use the map

Table 1.13: Spatial distribution parameters when NetCDF maps are provided

Parameter	Description
movement.netcdf.enabled	True if NetCDF maps are provided
movement.species.map#	Species to which the movement map is associated
movement.file.map#	NetCDF file containing the spatial distribution maps
movement.nsteps.year.map#	Number of time steps per year associated with the file.
movement.initialAge.map#	Minimum age (in years) when to use the map.
movement.lastAge.map#	Maximum age (in years) when to use the map.
movement.variable.map#	Name of the NetCDF variable containing the spatial distribution file.

One map is associated to a unique species for a given age span, year span and season. The full spatial distribution of a species can be represented using as many maps as necessary to cover different age spans and/or year spans and/or seasons. Let's now have a look at each parameter in detail.

Note that the CSV file has the same number of lines and columns as the OSMOSE grid. The distribution area can be defined using either a presence/absence map (1 for presence, 0 for absence) or a map of probability of presence (containing values ranging from 0 to values <1).

The same CSV file can be used to define different maps.

If the file path is set to null it means that the schools concerned by this map are out of the simulated domain (e.g., migrating species).

When a school comes back to the simulated area, it will be randomly located on a new map (the one corresponding to the species and age class of the school at the current time step of the simulation).

Several maps can be defined for representing the spatial distribution of a single species. For example:

```
#Map 0
movement.map0.species = euphausiids
movement.map0.file = maps/mymap_euphau1.csv
movement.map0.age.min = 0
movement.map0.age.max = 0.2
movement.map0.year.min = 0
movement.map0.year.max = 40
movement.map0.season = 0;1;2;3;4;5;6;7;8;9;10;11;12;13;14;15;16;17;18;19;20;21;22;23

#Map 1
```

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```

movement.map1.species = euphausiids
movement.map1.file = maps/mymap_euphau2.csv
movement.map1.age.min = 0.2
movement.map1.age.max = 1
movement.map1.year.min = 0
movement.map1.year.max = 40
movement.map1.season = 0;1;2;3;4;5;6;7;8;9

#Map 2
movement.map2.species = euphausiids
movement.map2.file = maps/mymap_euphau3.csv
movement.map2.age.min = 0.2
movement.map2.age.max = 1
movement.map2.year.min = 0
movement.map2.year.max = 40
movement.map2.season = 10;11;12;13;14;15;16;17;18;19;20;21;22;23

```

By increasing the number of maps, the description of the spatial distribution can be as detailed and refined as you want, as long as you have such information. It will allow for instance to create some maps for eggs (an egg in Osmose is a new school of age zero that is created during the reproduction process), some maps for the juveniles and some maps for the adults, as many as necessary to describe ontogenetic migrations.

From one time step to an other, the movement manager checks whether a given school remains in the same map or should “jump” to an other map (e.g. eggs map to juvenile map or adults in summer to adults in winter).

In the latter case (change of map), the schools are relocated randomly in the new map. The cell selection algorithm is as follows:

- A random cell ocean is selected, whose probability value is $P(i, j)$
- A random number is drafted, which is called R .
- If $P(i, j) < R \times P_{max}$, the operation is repeated. Else, the cell is selected.

In the former case (same map), the movement manager mimics foraging movement with a random-walk that moves schools to immediately adjacent cells within their distribution area.

1.7.5 Mortality

Within each time step, the total mortality of a given school is comprised of predation mortality caused by other schools, starvation mortality, fishing mortality, and diverse other natural mortality rate. The four different mortalities are computed so as to represent quasi simultaneous processes, and we consider that there is competition and stochasticity in the predation process.

Within each time step, OSMOSE considers each pair of school/source of mortality in turn in a random order. To ensure that the random order of the mortality sources and of the schools does not bias the resulting instantaneous mortality rates applied and effectively correspond to the mortality rates specified in input (for fishing and diverse natural mortality), all the mortality events are iterated within a time step over a fixed number of sub-time step.

Table 1.14: Mortality parameters

stochastic.mortality.seed	Integer to fix the random number generator.
mortality.subdt	Number of mortality sub time-steps.

Mortality processes are detailed below.

Fig. 1.6: Algorithm to select the cell where to move an unlocated school.

Predation mortality

The central assumption in OSMOSE is that predation is an opportunistic process, which depends on:

- the overlap between predators and potential prey items in the horizontal dimension
- size adequacy between the predators and the potential prey (determined by **predator/prey size ratios**); and when the information is available
- the accessibility of prey items to predators, which depends on their vertical distribution (this being determined by means of **accessibility coefficients**). Thus, in OSMOSE, the food web structure emerges from local predation and competition interactions.

During the predation mortality process, the predation success rate (predSuccessRate attribute) is updated.

Size predation

Size-predation matrix is controlled by two parameters. The predator school S_{pred} can only feed on prey schools whose length belongs to a given interval:

$$R_{max} < \frac{L_{pred}}{L_{prey}} \leq R_{min}$$

with R_{min} and R_{max} the maximum and minimum predator/prey size ratios. Reorganizing this inequality, we obtain:

$$\frac{L_{pred}}{R_{min}} \leq L_{prey} < \frac{L_{pred}}{R_{max}}$$

Therefore, the minimum and maximum sizes of a prey that a predator can eat is given by:

$$L_{max} = \frac{L_{pred}}{R_{max}}$$

$$L_{min} = \frac{L_{pred}}{R_{min}}$$

Table 1.15: Size-predation parameters

predation.predPrey.stage.structure	Structure to determine thresholds for predator/prey size ratios (age or size)
predation.predPrey.stage.threshold.sp#	Array of age or size thresholds
predation.predPrey.sizeRatio.max.sp#	Array of R_{max} values
predation.predPrey.sizeRatio.min.sp#	Array of R_{min} values

Danger: To make sure that $L_{max} < L_{min}$, the `predation.predPrey.sizeRatio.max.sp#` and `predation.predPrey.sizeRatio.min.sp#` must verify $R_{min} > R_{max}$

Since resource groups are defined by a range of sizes, and not by a single sizes, the predator will feed on a given percentage of the resource:

$$R_{rsc} = \frac{\min(L_{max_{rsc}}, L_{max}) - \max(L_{min_{rsc}}, L_{min})}{L_{max_{rsc}} - L_{min_{rsc}}}$$

which is the overlapping range of the predator accessible range and of the resource size range.

Fig. 1.7: Size-based predation in Osmose

Accessibility

First, the accessibility of all the preys to a given school is determined from an accessibility matrix for every species and stages. This matrix must not be used to define diet preferences but rather to take into account for a difference of positions in the water column (meaning some schools might evolve around the same geographical area but never meet because they do not occur at the same depth).

Table 1.16: Example of a CSV predation accessibility file.

Prey / Predator	lesserSpotted < 0.45	lesserSpotted	redMullet < 0.25	redMullet
lesserSpottedDogfish < 0.45	0.05	0	0	0.05
lesserSpottedDogfish	0	0.8	0.4	0
redMullet < 0.25	0	0.4	0.8	0
redMullet	0.8	0.4	0	0.8
pouting < 0.25	0	0.4	0.8	0
pouting	0	0.8	0.4	0
whiting < 0.25	0	0.4	0.8	0
whiting	0	0.8	0.4	0
Dinoflagellates	0	0.5	1	0
Diatoms	0	0.5	1	0
Microzoo	0	0.5	1	0
Mesozoo	0	0.5	1	0
Macrozoo	0	0.5	1	0
VSBVerySmallBenthos	1	0.5	0	1
SmallBenthos	1	0.5	0	1
MediumBenthos	1	0.5	0	1
LargeBenthos	1	0.5	0	1
VLBVeryLargeBenthos	1	0.5	0	1
backgroundSpecies	0	0	0	0

Each line of the matrix corresponds to a prey (including plankton groups), and each column to a predator. The file must be understood as follow: lesserSpottedDogfish of age class less than 0.45 (line 1) are only accessible to young lesserSpottedDogfish (5%) and old redMullet (5%).

The class thresholds (age or size, defined with the `predation.accessibility.stage.structure` parameter) that are used to determine which row or column should be used are read directly from the CSV files by matching the `<` character. It is assumed that if there is no match, no threshold is provided. However, when `<` is matched, it is assumed that the number that follows is the upper bound of the class.

Furthermore, the column and row order is not important, since a match of the species name is performed.

Additionally, accessibility matrix can vary over time. To do so, one set of parameters must be defined for each accessibility matrix, as done for the parameterization of movements. The keys of these parameters must end with `.acc#`, with `#` the number of the accessibility matrix.

Table 1.17: Parameters for accessibility matrix

predation.accessibility.stage.structure	Threshold type. Must be <code>age</code> or <code>size</code> .
predation.accessibility.file	CSV file containing the accessibility matrix if constant over time
predation.accessibility.file.acc#	CSV file containing the accessibility matrix for the accessibility matrix #
predation.accessibility.initialYear.acc#	Start year when to use the accessibility matrix #
predation.accessibility.finalYear.acc#	Start year when to use the accessibility matrix #
predation.accessibility.years.acc#	List of years when to use the accessibility matrix # (instead of setting initial and final years)
predation.accessibility.steps.acc#	List of time steps when to use the accessibility matrix #

Danger: If the `predation.accessibility.file` (with no `.acc` suffix) is found, Osmose will assume constant predation accessibility matrix.

Predation rate

Finally, the predation rate is computed as follows. First, the total accessible biomass for the predator school is computed:

$$B_{avail} = \sum_{p=preys} A(pred, prey) \times B_{prey}$$

where B_{avail} is the total accessible biomass of preys, $A(pred, prey)$ is the accessibility coefficient of the predator over the given prey (cf. Section 1.7.5) and B_{prey} is the biomass of the prey.

The total biomass that a predator can eat is also computed as follow:

$$B_{eatable} = \frac{B_{pred} \times I_{max}}{N_{mort}}$$

with N_{mort} the number of sub-step of mortality processes, B_{pred} the total biomass of predator and I_{max} the maximum ingestion rate for each species, expressed in grams of food per gram of fish and per year. It is assumed that predator eat as much as they can.

The effective biomass that will be eaten by the predator is

$$B_{eaten} = \min(B_{avail}, B_{eatable})$$

The success rate for the given time-step ($S_R(t)$) is incremented by then the value computed for the given sub time-step as:

$$S_R(t) = S_R(t) + \frac{B_{eaten}}{B_{eatable}}$$

Finally, for each prey, the biomass eaten by the predator is given by:

$$B_{lostprey} = B_{eaten} \times \frac{A(pred, prey) \times B_{prey}}{B_{avail}}$$

and used to increment the number of dead individuals by predation (nDead attribute).

Table 1.18: Ingestion parameter

predation.ingestion.rate.max.sp#	I_{max} (grams of food per gram of fish and per year)
----------------------------------	---

Starvation mortality

Starvation mortality is applied as follows:

$$N_{starv} = N \times (1 - e^{-M_{starv}})$$

with M_{starv} the starvation mortality rate, which is computed as follows:

$$M_{starv} = M_{max} \times \left(1 - \frac{S_R}{C_{S_R}}\right) \text{ if } S_R \leq C_{S_R}$$

Note: Starvation mortality rate applied at time step t is based on the predation success computed at time-step $t - 1$

Table 1.19: Starvation mortality parameters

mortality.starvation.rate.max.sp#	Maximum rate of starvation mortality M_{max}
predation.encycritical.sp#	Critical predation success rate C_{S_R}

Migration mortality

When a school is out of the domain, none of the standards processes (predation, growth, fishing, natural mortality, growth, starvation) apply.

The migration mortality is used to simulate all sources of mortality outside the simulated area. It applies as long as the school is located out of the simulated area

$$N_{out} = N \times (1 - e^{-M_{out}})$$

Table 1.20: Parameters for migration mortality

mortality.out.rate.sp#	Annual mortality rate for species that move out of the simulated area (M_{out})
------------------------	---

Fishing mortality

In Osmose, there are two implementations of the fishing mortality:

- One in which fishing mortality is by-species. It is the implementation that has been used so far. In this implementation, bycatch, discards and size-selectivities are not taken into account.
- One in which fishing mortality is by-gear. In this case, bycatch and discards can be taken into account through a catchability matrix. Additionally, size-selectivity can be explicitly considered.

By-species fishing mortality

On Osmose versions **previous** to 4.0.0, fishing mortality was species-specific. It was parameterized either by providing fishing rates or catches.

Table 1.21: Fishing parameters (< 4.0.0)

mortality.fishing.type	Whether fishing mortality is provided as rate or catches
mortality.fishing.recruitment.age.sp#	Age at which a species can be fished (years)
mortality.fishing.recruitment.size.sp#	Size at which a species can be fished (cm)

Warning: Osmose does not accept fishing mortality rates for some species and catches for other species.

By rate

If mortality rate is provided, the number of dead fishes in a school is computed as follows.

$$N_{fishing} = N \times (1 - \exp^{-F})$$

Osmose offers several degrees of refinement for inputting the fishing mortality: constant, seasonal, interannual and interannual with age or size class. Depending on the available information for each species of the configuration, one must choose the best way to input it. Each species can be parameterized independently from an other. For instance fishing mortality for species zero is a constant annual rate and fishing mortality for species three is provided as a time series per size class.

Table 1.22: Parameters for fishing rate.

mortality.fishing.rate.byDt.byAge.file.sp#	CSV file containing the fishing rates by age and by time-step
mortality.fishing.rate.byDt.bySize.file.sp#	CSV file containing the fishing rates by size and by time-step
mortality.fishing.rate.byYear.file.sp#	File containing the fishing rates by year
mortality.fishing.rate.sp#	Annual fishing rate
mortality.fishing.season.distrib.file.sp#	File containing the seasonal distribution of fishing mortality. If not provided, assumes constant fishing rate

Osmose will first look for any of the first two parameters. If not found, it will look for the third one. If not found, Osmose will finally look for the fourth one. If the third or fourth parameter are found, it will also look for the fifth one.

By catches

If mortality is provided by catches, the number dead individuals is computed as follows:

$$N_{fish} = \min \left(N, C \times \frac{B_{fish}}{B_{fishable} \times W} \right) \text{ if } B_{fishable} > 0$$

with C the catches, B_{fish} the fish biomass, W its weight and $B_{fishable}$ the biomass that can be fished.

Table 1.23: Parameters for fishing catches.

mortality.fishing.catches.byDt.byAge.file.sp#	CSV file containing the fishing rates by age and by time-step
mortality.fishing.catches.byDt.bySize.file.sp#	CSV file containing the fishing rates by size and by time-step
mortality.fishing.catches.byYear.file.sp#	File containing the fishing rates by year
mortality.fishing.catches.sp#	Annual fishing rate
mortality.fishing.season.distrib.file.sp#	File containing the seasonal distribution of fishing mortality

Note: Catches are assumed to be in tons.

Osmose will first look for any of the first two parameters. If not found, it will look for the third one. If not found, Osmose will finally look for the fourth one. If the third or fourth parameter are found, it will also look for the fifth one.

Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)

The user can defined as many MPA as he wishes.

Table 1.24: Parameters for setting MPA

mpa.file.mpa#	File containing the MPA definition
mpa.start.year.mpa#	First year when this MPA is active
mpa.end.year.mpa#	Last year when this MPA is active

The map is a CSV file similar to the movement maps. The CSV file has the same number of lines and columns as the OSMOSE grid. The MPA file must contain 1 where the MPA is defined, 0 elsewhere.

Start year and end year parameters define the time span when the MPA is enabled.

The MPA are handled within the fishing process. Every time there is a new MPA to be activated or deactivated, Osmose updates the correction factor that will be applied to the fishing mortality rates in order to take into account the uniform redistribution of the fishing effort outside the MPAs.

By-gear fishing mortality

Fishing mortality rates

In the Osmose versions ≥ 4.3 , changes in the parameterization of fisheries have been implemented, although the spirit remains close to the one in versions 4.

Fisheries mortality time-series for each gear are now the product of three components:

- A vector of fishing mortality rates associated with fishing periods, F_{period}
- A vector of seasonality values, which provides the time-variation of the fishing effort during a given season, F_{season}
- A vector of multipliers, which provides a multiplication factor, F_{base} .

Therefore, for a given time-step t , the value of the fishing mortality for a given fleet would be:

$$F(t) = F_{period}(t) \times F_{season}(t) \times F_{base}(t)$$

Since the parameterisation is a bit tricky, a parameter (`fisheries.check.enabled`) allows to control whether the values of F , F_{period} , F_{season} and F_{base} should be saved. It allows to control that the given time-series are as expected.

Fishing base

The fishing base mortality multiplier (F_{base}) is provided as regime shifts.

Table 1.25: Fishing base parameters

fisheries.rate.base.fsh#	Fishing base for the different regimes.
fisheries.rate.base.shift.fsh#	Years of the regime shifts.
fisheries.rate.base.log.enabled.fsh#	True if fisheries are provided in logscale.

If one value is provided in `fisheries.rate.base.fsh#`, this value will be used during all the simulation. If N values are provided, then the `fisheries.rate.base.shift.fsh#` parameter must contain $N - 1$ values, which are the years of the regime shifts.

Fishing period

There is now the possibility to define a fishing period (F_{period}), i.e. a period when the fishery is active.

Table 1.26: Fishing period parameters

fisheries.period.number.fsh#	Number of fishing periods within one year (N_{per})
fisheries.period.start.fsh#	Start of the active fishing period (fraction of year, default = 0, Y_{start})
fisheries.rate.byperiod.fsh#	Fishing mortality rate. Must be in $year^{-1}$

Note that the number of values expected in the `fisheries.rate.byperiod.fsh#` parameter depends on Y_{start} .

If $Y_{start} = 0$, then $N_{per} \times N_{year}$ values are expected (one value for each fishing and non-fishing season).

If $Y_{start} \neq 0$, then $N_{per} \times N_{year} + 1$ values are expected.

Fig. 1.8: Fishing period for two values of Y_{start}

Fishing seasonality

In order to distribute the fishery mortality over the season, the user can define a seasonality vector, either as a file, or as a vector.

Table 1.27: Fishing seasonality parameters

fisheries.seasonality.fsh#	Array of fishing seasonality. Must contain $\frac{N_{step/year}}{N_{season}}$
fisheries.seasonality.file.fsh#	File containing the fishing seasonalities (must contain N_{step} values)

In the first case, the same seasonality will be applied for each fishing season. Imagine that we have 24 time-steps per year and two fishing season (with no offset, top of figure Fig. 1.8), then the seasonality provided should contain 12 values, which would apply for the active fishing period (green zone).

In the latter case, it is up to the user to generate the proper time series and to store it in a file.

Danger: The sum of fishing seasonalities must equal one over the fishing seasons! **No automatic normalisation is performed by Osmose!**

Case studies

```
fisheries.rate.base.fsh0;1
fisheries.season.number.fsh0;1
fisheries.rate.byperiod.fsh0;1
fisheries.season.start.fsh0;0
fisheries.seasonality.fsh0;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.
↪04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.
↪0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166;0.04166
```

```
fisheries.rate.base.fsh0;1
fisheries.season.number.fsh0;2
fisheries.rate.byperiod.fsh0;1, 0, 2, 0, 3, 0, 4, 0, 5, 0
fisheries.season.start.fsh0;0
fisheries.seasonality.fsh0;0.0;0.0;0.0;0.0;0.0;0.0;0.1666;0.1666;0.1666;0.1666;0.1666;0.
↪1666;
```

```
fisheries.rate.base.fsh0;1
fisheries.season.number.fsh0;2
fisheries.rate.byperiod.fsh0;0, 1, 0, 2, 0, 3, 0, 4, 0, 5, 0
fisheries.season.start.fsh0;0.25
fisheries.seasonality.fsh0;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.
↪0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;
```

```
fisheries.rate.base.fsh0;1,2,3,10
fisheries.rate.base.shift.fsh0;1, 3, 4
fisheries.season.number.fsh0;2
fisheries.rate.byperiod.fsh0;0, 1, 0, 2, 0, 3, 0, 4, 0, 5, 0
fisheries.season.start.fsh0;0.25
fisheries.seasonality.fsh0;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.
↪0833;0.0833;0.0833;0.0833;
```

```
fisheries.rate.base.fsh0;1,2,3,10
fisheries.rate.base.shift.fsh0;1, 3, 4
fisheries.season.number.fsh0;3
fisheries.rate.byperiod.fsh0;0, 1, 0, 2, 0, 3, 0, 4, 0, 5, 0, 6, 0, 7, 0, 8
fisheries.season.start.fsh0;0.25
fisheries.seasonality.fsh0;0.1,0.2,0.5,0.2,0,0,0,0
```


Size selectivities

Table 1.28: Fishing size-selectivity parameters

fisheries.selectivity.tiny.fsh#	Selectivities values below which selectivity is forced to 0 (ϵ)
fish-eries.selectivity.type.file.fsh#	File containing the selectivity types
fish-eries.selectivity.type.shift.fsh#	Array containing the selectivity periods
fisheries.selectivity.type.fsh#	Selectivity types (one value per shift period). Must be 0, 1 or 2
fish-eries.selectivity.a50.file.fsh#	File containing the age selectivities.
fish-eries.selectivity.a50.shift.fsh#	Array containing the A_{50} shift periods
fisheries.selectivity.a50.fsh#	Age selectivity (one value per shift period). If set, assumes that fishery selectivity is age-based
fish-eries.selectivity.150.file.fsh#	File containing the L_{50} .
fish-eries.selectivity.150.shift.fsh#	Array containing the L_{50} shift periods
fisheries.selectivity.150.fsh#	L_{50} (one value per shift period).
fish-eries.selectivity.175.file.fsh#	File containing the L_{75}
fish-eries.selectivity.175.shift.fsh#	Array containing the L_{75} shift periods
fisheries.selectivity.175.fsh#	L_{75} (one value per shift period).

Note that `type`, `a50`, `150` and `175` are parameterized in the same way. If the `.file` parameter is defined, then it is used. If it is not set, then values are defined by using the other two parameters. The `shift` array contains thresholds, where the values are to change.

The selectivity type must contain 0 (knife-edge), 1 (sigmoid), 2 (Gaussian) or 3 (log-normal).

If one of the `a50` parameter, it is assumed that age selectivity is used.

Warning: Only knife-edge selectivity can be used with age.

Note: If only knife-edge selectivity is used, then the `175` parameters are not used.

Knife-edge selectivity

Knife-edge selectivity is computed as follows:

$$S(L) = 1 \text{ if } L \geq L_{50}$$

Sigmoid selectivity

Sigmoid selectivity is computed as follows:

$$S(L) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp^{S_1 - S_2 L}}$$

$$S_1 = \frac{L_{50} \times \ln 3}{L_{75} - L_{50}}$$

$$S_2 = \frac{S_1}{L_{50}}$$

Gaussian selectivity

Gaussian selectivity is computed as follows:

$$S(L) = \frac{F(L)}{F(L_{50})}$$

$$F(L) = \exp\left(-\frac{L - L_{50}}{2\sigma^2}\right)$$

$$\sigma = \frac{L_{75} - L_{50}}{q_{75}}$$

with q_{75} is the inverse cumulative standard normal distribution for the 75th percentile.

Catchability

Fishery catchabilities are parameterized in a similar way as predation accessibility matrix.

Table 1.29: Fisheries catchabilities

fisheries.catchability.file	Name of the catchability file
fisheries.catchability.file.cat#	Name of the catchability file
fisheries.catchability.years.cat#	List of years when the catchability should be used.
fish-eries.catchability.initialYear.cat#	First year when the catchability matrix should be used (if year list not provided)
fisheries.catchability.finalYear.cat#	Last year when the catchability matrix should be used (if year list not provided)
fisheries.catchability.steps.cat#	List of steps within a year when the catchability should be used.

Fishery catchabilities should be provided as a CSV file, with fisheries as column (predators) and species (background and focal) as rows (preys). If the first parameter (`fisheries.catchability.file`) is found, then this catchability matrix will be used over the entire simulation.

If this parameter is not found, Osmose will assume that catchability matrixes may vary over time. It will therefore look for all the fisheries.catchability.file.cat# parameters. Each catchability matrix should be associated with time-indications, which specifies on which year (interannual variability) and which time-steps (seasonal variability) this catchability matrix should be used.

Warning: Note that the # here is not related to the one of fisheries.

Discards

There is also the possibility to define fisheries discards. It is defined in the same way as catchabilities (cf above for a detailed description of the parameters).

Table 1.30: Fisheries discards

fisheries.discards.file	Name of the catchability file
fisheries.discards.file.dis#	Name of the catchability file
fisheries.discards.initialYear.dis#	First year when the catchability matrix should be used
fisheries.discards.finalYear.dis#	Last year when the catchability matrix should be used
fisheries.discards.years.dis#	List of years when the catchability should be used.
fisheries.discards.steps.dis#	List of steps within a year when the catchability should be used.

Fishery discards should be provided as a CSV file, with fisheries as column (predators) and species (background and focal) as rows (preys).

Note: It is possible to mimic the by-species implementation with the by-gear one, by providing a diagonal catchability matrix and knife-edge selectivities

1.7.6 Growth

Individuals of a given school are assumed to grow in size and weight at a given time only when the amount of food they ingested fulfill maintenance requirements, i.e., only when their predation efficiency at that time is greater than the predation efficiency ensuring body maintenance of school.

$$G(s, a) = M_{\Delta}(s, a) \times \frac{S_R(s, a) - C_{S_R}(s)}{1 - C_{S_R}(s)} \text{ if } S_R(s, a) \geq C_{S_R}$$

$$G(s, a) = 0 \text{ if } S_R(s, a) < C_{S_R}$$

with C_{S_R} is the critical predation efficiency and S_R the predation success rate of the school.

$M_{\Delta}(s, a) = \lambda \times \Delta L(a)$ is the maximum growth rate at age a and for species s .

$\Delta L(a) = L(a+1) - L(a)$ is the mean length increase determined from a growth function (Von Bertalanffy or Gompertz growth function), while λ is a factor that allows to control the maximum length at a given age.

Table 1.31: Growth parameters

growth.java.classname.sp#	Class name of the age to length conversion
predation.efficiency.critical.sp#	Critical predation success (C_{S_R})
species.delta.lmax.factor.sp#	λ (default = 2)

Von Bertalanffy growth

When the `growth.java.classname.sp#` is equal to `fr.ird.osmose.process.growth.VonBertalanffyGrowth.java`, a von Bertalanffy growth function is used. **It is the default one.**

$$L(a) = L_{egg} \text{ if } a = 0$$

$$L(a) = L_{egg} + (L_{thres} - L_{egg}) \times \left(\frac{a}{a_{thres}} \right) \text{ if } a > 0 \text{ \& } a < a_{thres}$$

$$L(a) = L_{\infty} \times \left(1 - \exp^{-K(age-t_0)} \right) \text{ else}$$

with

$$L_{thres} = \min \left[L_{egg}, L_{\infty} \times \left(1 - \exp^{-K(a_{thres}-t_0)} \right) \right]$$

A Von Bertalanffy model is used to calculate mean length increase above a threshold age a_{thres} determined for each HTL group from the literature. Below a_{thres} , a simple linear model is used. The rationale behind this is that Von Bertalanffy parameters are usually estimated from data excluding youngs of the year or including only very few of them. Assuming a linear growth between age 0 and a_{thres} ensures a more realistic calculation of mean length increases for early ages of HTL groups ([Travers *et al.*, 2009]).

Fig. 1.9: Von Bertalanffy growth curve

Table 1.32: Von Bertalanffy parameters

species.linf.sp#	L_{inf} (cm)
species.k.sp#	K
species.t0.sp#	t_0
species.vonbertalanffy.threshold.age.sp#	a_{thres} (years, default=1 year)

Gompertz growth

When the `growth.java.classname.sp#` is equal to `fr.ird.osmose.process.growth.GompertzGrowth.java`, a Gompertz growth function is used.

$$\begin{aligned}
 L(a) &= L_{egg} \text{ if } a = 0 \\
 L(a) &= L_{start} \times \exp^{K_e \times a} \text{ if } a > 0 \ \& \ a < a_{exp} \\
 L(a) &= L_{exp} + (L_{gom} - L_{exp}) \frac{a - a_{exp}}{a_{gom} - a_{exp}} \text{ if } a > a_{exp} \ \& \ a < a_{gom} \\
 L(a) &= L_{inf} \times \exp^{-\exp^{-K_g(a-t_g)}} \text{ else}
 \end{aligned}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{exp} &= L_{start} \times \exp^{K_e \times a_{exp}} \\
 L_{gom} &= L_{inf} \times \exp^{-\exp^{-K_g(a_{gom}-t_g)}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 1.33: Gompertz parameters

growth.exponential.lstart.sp#	L_{start} (cm)
growth.exponential.ke.sp#	K_e
growth.gompertz.linf.sp#	L_{inf} (cm)
growth.gompertz.kg.sp#	K_g
growth.gompertz.tg.sp#	t_g (years)
growth.exponential.thr.age.sp#	a_{exp} (years)
growth.gompertz.thr.age.sp#	a_{gom} (years)

1.7.7 Reproduction

The system starts from a pristine state, with no schools in the domain. For a few years (user-defined), Osmose will release some eggs for every species. The eggs enter the different steps of the life cycle, and once the fish reach sexual maturity, the reproduction process takes over. Osmose stops the seeding, unless the spawning stock biomass gets depleted. In that case Osmose resumes the seeding by releasing some eggs until there are again mature individuals in the system for carrying on the reproduction process. Osmose completely ceases the seeding when the simulation reaches the maximal number of years for seeding (user-defined).

For a given species:

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{mat} &= \sum_{mature \ sch.} B \\
 N_{eggs} &= FRAC_{fem} \times \alpha \times season \times B_{mat} \text{ if } SSB > 0 \\
 N_{eggs} &= FRAC_{fem} \times \alpha \times season \times B_{seeding} \text{ if } SSB = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

By following this approach:

Fig. 1.10: Gompertz growth curve

- No assumption is made about the structure of the populations but it emerges from individual interactions
- it reduces computing requirements for the spin-up as the first years are the fastest to run
- it reduces the number of time steps for the spin-up
- it minimizes the amplitude of population oscillations

Finally, the seeding biomass is then used to add new schools to the system, depending on the value of N_{eggs} .

If $N_{eggs} < N_s$:

$$N_{sch} = 1$$

$$A_{sch} = N_{eggs}$$

else:

$$N_{sch} = N_s$$

$$A_{sch} = \frac{N_{eggs}}{N_s}$$

Table 1.34: Reproduction paramters

simulation.nschool.sp#	Number of schools of species # to create during reproduction (N_s)
simulation.nschool	Number of schools to create during reproduction (N_s). Used if no species specific value provided
popula- tion.seeding.biomass.sp#	Seeding biomass ($B_{seeding}$, tons)
reproduc- tion.season.file.sp#	File providing the seeding distribution within a year
species.sexratio.sp#	Fraction of females ($FRAC_{fem}$)
species.relativefecundity.sp#	Number of eggs per gram of mature female (relative fecundity)
popula- tion.seeding.year.max	Number of years when the artificial seeding is activated

BIOEN-OSMOSE ODD DESCRIPTION

The present section contains all the necessary information and guidelines to help understand the principles and assumptions of the Bioenergetic version (BIOEN-OSMOSE) version of the OSMOSE model, apply it to a specific case study and run simulations for addressing specific issues.

2.1 Design concepts

2.1.1 Basic principles

Individuals' bioenergetics are described according to a biphasic growth model [Andersen, 2019, Boukal *et al.*, 2014, Quince *et al.*, 2008] in which body mass-dependent energy fluxes are allocated between competing processes—namely maintenance, somatic growth and gonadic growth—thus accounting for physiological trade-offs that constrain both phenotypically plastic and evolutionary responses of life-history traits to selective pressures [Roff, 1922, Stearns, 1992]. Sexual maturation of individuals relies on the concept of maturation reaction norms that depicts how the process of maturation responds plastically to variation in body growth [Heino *et al.*, 2002, Stearns and Koella, 1986]. This combination mechanistically describes the processes of somatic growth, sexual maturation and reproduction as they emerge from energy fluxes sustained by food intake resulting from size-based opportunistic predation.

On top of the biphasic growth model, individuals' energy mobilization and maintenance energetic costs depend on dissolved oxygen concentration and temperature in a way that the resulting metabolic rate (the net energy available for new tissue production) and thus somatic and gonadic growth conform to the oxygen- and capacity-limited thermal tolerance theory (OCLTT; Pörtner [2001]) and more generally to thermal performance curves (TPC; Angilletta Jr and Angilletta [2009]). In short, oxygen delivery to mitochondria is a limiting factor of Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) synthesis and thus of the mobilization of the energy contained in chemical bonds of assimilated molecules [Clarke, 2017]. Therefore, dissolved oxygen saturation in water sets up an upper limit to energy mobilization. Moreover, beyond a temperature range within which energy mobilization increases with temperature due to chemical reaction rate acceleration, the limitation in ventilation and circulation capacity of individuals as temperature increases is such that oxygen uptake and delivery for energy mobilization saturates or even decreases at high temperatures, potentially due to temperature dependence of the rate of enzyme-catalyzed chemical reactions [Arcus *et al.*, 2016] or enzyme denaturation [Pawar *et al.*, 2015]. In contrast, maintenance energetic costs increase with temperature exponentially according to the Arrhenius law [Brown *et al.*, 2004, Gillooly *et al.*, 2002, Kooijman, 2009]. It results that when temperature increases above the individual preferred temperature, energy mobilization increases slower than maintenance costs resulting mechanistically in a dome-shaped relationship between net energy rate for tissue production (which results from energy mobilization minus maintenance costs) and temperature that conforms to OCLTT and TPC. These bioenergetic responses to ambient oxygen and temperature translate into plastic responses of the life-history processes (growth, maturation and reproduction) that emerge from the energy allocation scheme described by the biphasic growth model but also into selective pressures as individuals will incur “energetic starvation” mortality when net energy rate is negative and cannot be covered by energy reserves contained in gonads.

Finally, individuals exhibit adaptive behavior in their movements by avoiding foraging in locations of adverse conditions of dissolved oxygen and temperature [Townhill *et al.*, 2017] that would impair their net energy rate to the point of certain

energetic starvation, thus conforming to the hypothesis of metabolic constraints on marine habitat and biogeography [Deutsch *et al.*, 2015, Deutsch *et al.*, 2020]

2.2 Entities, state variables, and scales

2.2.1 Entities

- The EnergyBudget entity describes the parameters and the bioenergetic processes of BIOEN-OSMOSE.
- The TempFunction entity describes the parameters and the temperature-related processes of BIOEN-OSMOSE.
- The OxygenFunction entity describes the parameters and the oxygen-related processes of BIOEN-OSMOSE.

2.2.2 State variables

EnergyBudget

The EnergyBudget entity contains the following state variables:

Table 2.1: EnergyBudget state variables in BIOEN-OSMOSE

Variable	Description	Type	Units
c_m	Array of mass-specific maintenance rate (one for each species)	float[]	$g.year^{-1}$
m0	Array of intercept of a deterministic linear maturation reaction norm (one for each species)	float[]	cm
m1	Array of slope of a deterministic linear maturation reaction norm (one for each species)	float[]	$cm.year^{-1}$
eta	Array of energy density ratio between somatic and gonadic tissue	float[]	
temp_function	Temperature function entity	TemperatureFunction	
oxygen_function	Oxygen function entity	OxygenFunction	
r	Array of gonado-somatic index of school		
larvaePredation-RateBioen	Array of multiplication factor for ingestion of larva individuals	float[]	
assimilation	Array of assimilation efficiency	float[]	

TempFunction

The TempFunction entity contains the following state variables:

Table 2.2: TempFunction state variables in BIOEN-OSMOSE

Variable	Description	Type	Units
e_M	Array of increasing activation energy of the energy mobilization temperature function	float[]	J
e_D	Array of declining activation energy of the energy mobilization temperature function	float[]	J
Tp	Array of temperature of peak value in energy mobilization	float[]	C
e_m	Activation energy of the maintenance temperature function	float[]	J
temperature_input	Temperature input dataset	PhysicalData	
isPhiTActivated	True if the mobilized energy should depend on temperature	bool, default is true	

OxygenFunction

The `OxygenFunction` entity contains the following state variables:

Table 2.3: OxygenFunction state variables in BIOEN-OSMOSE

Variable	Description	Type	Units
c1	Array of asymptote of energy mobilization dose-response function to dissolved oxygen saturation	float[]	
c2	Array of slope of energy mobilization dose-response function to dissolved oxygen saturation	float[]	
o2_input	Oxygen dataset	PhysicalData	
isFO2Activated	True if the oxygen function should be used in the ingestion formula	bool, default is true	

School

The `Species` entity contains the following state variables:

Table 2.4: Species state variables in BIOEN-OSMOSE

Variable	Description	Type	Units
zlayer	Index of the temperature/oxygen layer to read	int	
sizeMaturity	Size at maturity	float, set to ∞	cm
ageMaturity	Age at maturity	float, set to ∞	year
eggSize	Size of eggs	float, set to ∞	cm
beta_bioen	Scaling exponent of maximum ingestion rate and maintenance rate with body mass	float	

School

The School entity contains the following state variables:

Table 2.5: School state variables in BIOEN-OSMOSE

Variable	Description	Type	Units
e_gross	Mobilized energy rate of individuals of school at time step	float	g / timestep
e_maint	Maintenance cost rate of individuals of school at time step	float	g / timestep
e_net	Net energy available for new tissue production	float	g / timestep
ingestion	Ingestion rate of individuals in school at time step	float	g / timestep
ingestionTot	Sum of all the food ingested during life of the school	float	g
kappa	Proportion of new tissues allocated to the gonadic compartment	float	
e_net_faced	Mean net energy faced during lifespan of the school	float	g
mort_starv_rate			
mort_oxy_rate			

2.3 Submodels

2.3.1 Energy uptake, assimilation and mobilization

For an individual in school i , the energy uptake from food at time step t is described by a Holling's type 1 functional response f (Holling [1959]) that depends on its somatic mass $w(i, t)$ (Christensen and Walters [2004], Holt and Jørgensen [2014], Shin and Cury [2004]) in two ways.

First, it determines prey food biomass $P(i, t)$ available to an individual of school i from the other schools and lower trophic levels present in the same grid cell $c(i, t)$ according to a minimum $R_{min}(s(i))$ and a maximum $R_{max}(s(i))$ predator to prey size ratio (Shin and Cury [2004], Travers *et al.* [2009]):

$$P(i, t) = \frac{\sum_j \gamma(s(i), s(j)) B(j, t)}{N(i, t)}$$

with

$$j \in \left(j \vee (c(j, t) = c(i, t)) \left(\frac{L(i, t)}{R_{max}(i)} \leq L(j, t) \leq \frac{L(i, t)}{R_{min}(i)} \right) \right)$$

where $\gamma(s(i), s(j))$ is the accessibility coefficient essentially determined by the position of potential prey schools j in the water column relative to that of school i and $B(j, t) = N(j, t)w(j, t)$ is the biomass of prey school j . Second, it sets the maximum possible ingestion rate according to an allometric function with a scaling exponent β . The energy uptake can then be written as:

$$I(i, t) = f(P(i, t)) = \min(P(i, t); I_{max}(i)\psi(i, t)w(i, t)^\beta$$

with $I_{max}(i)$ the maximum ingestion rate per mass unit at exponent β (or mass-specific maximum ingestion rate) of individuals in school i and $\psi(i, t)$ a multiplicative factor that depends of their life stage according to:

$$\psi(i, t) = \begin{cases} \theta & \text{if } a(i, t) < a_l \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where a_l is age at the end of a fast growth period (e.g larval period or the larval and post-larval period) and θ a factor accounting for higher mass-specific maximum ingestion rate at this stage. A portion ξ of the energy uptake $I(i, t)$ is assimilated, a fraction $1 - \xi$ being lost due to excretion and faeces egestion.

Fig. 2.1: Summary of the processes at stake in the Bioen-OSMOSE version.

No reserves are modeled in EV-OSMOSE, hence all the assimilated energy can be directly mobilized. Mobilized energy E_M , referred to as active metabolic rate in the ecophysiology literature, fuels all metabolic processes such as maintenance, digestion, foraging, somatic growth, gonadic growth, etc... The mobilization of energy relies on the use of oxygen to transform the energy held in the chemical bonds of nutrients into a usable form, namely ATP [Clarke, 2019]. In consequence, the maximum possible energy mobilized at a given temperature depends directly on dissolved oxygen saturation and, as temperature increases, on the capacity of individuals to sustain oxygen uptake and delivery for ATP production (see section 1.2.1 Basic principles for more details). The mobilized energy rate E_M is thus described by

$$E_M(i, t) = \xi I(i, t) \lambda([O_2](i, t)) \varphi_M(T(i, t))$$

with $\lambda([O_2](i, t))$ and $\varphi_M(T(i, t))$ being the mobilization responses to dissolved oxygen saturation and temperature encountered by school i in the grid cell it occupies at time t . These are scaled between 0 and 1 such that, in optimal conditions, all assimilated energy $E_M(i, t) = \xi I(i, t)$ can be mobilized and, in suboptimal conditions, only a fraction of assimilated energy can be mobilized ($E_M(i, t) < \xi I(i, t)$). More precisely, the effect of dissolved oxygen is described by a dose-response function λ [Thomas *et al.*, 2019] which increases with the saturation of dissolved oxygen:

$$\lambda([O_2]) = C_{O,1} \frac{[O_2]}{[O_2] + C_{O,2}}$$

with $C_{O,1}$ and $C_{O,2}$ the asymptote and the slope of the dose-response function.

The effect of temperature is described according to the Johnson and Lewin [1946] model [Pawar *et al.*, 2015]:

$$\varphi_M(T) = \Phi \frac{e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_M}{k_B T}}}{1 + \frac{\varepsilon_M}{\varepsilon_D - \varepsilon_M} e^{\frac{\varepsilon_D}{k_B} \left(\frac{1}{T_P} - \frac{1}{T} \right)}}$$

with k_B the Boltzmann constant, ε_M the activation energy for the Arrhenius-like increase in mobilized energy with temperature T before reaching its peak value at T_P , ε_D the activation energy for the energy mobilization decline with T after T_P , and

$$\Phi = \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon_M}{\varepsilon_D - \varepsilon_M} \right) e^{\frac{\varepsilon_M}{k_B T}}$$

a standardizing constant insuring that $\varphi_M(T_P) = 1$.

The thermal responses of the bioenergetic fluxes is summarized in Fig. 2.2

2.3.2 Maintenance

The mobilized energy E_M fuels all metabolic processes starting in priority with the costs of maintenance of existing tissues E_m , which is often referred to as the standard metabolic rate in ecophysiology literature. Here, we include in maintenance costs also routine activities of individuals including foraging and digestion, so that they might be compared to routine metabolic rate in the ecophysiology literature. The maintenance costs are explicitly modeled to describe the share of mobilized energy between maintenance and the production of new tissues [Charnov *et al.*, 2001, Holt and Jørgensen, 2014, Mollet *et al.*, 2010], with precedence of the former over the latter, as well as to link mechanistically starvation mortality to energetic starvation when neither mobilized energy nor gonad energy reserves can cover the costs of maintenance (see next section New tissue production for more details).

The maintenance energy rate E_m scales with individual's somatic mass $w(i, t)$ with the same exponent as maximum ingestion rate. Thus, for a given temperature, the production of new tissues, and notably somatic growth, is not limited by disproportionately increasing maintenance costs relative to ingestion rate as somatic mass increases [Lefevre *et al.*,

Fig. 2.2: Thermal responses of the bioenergetic fluxes from ingestion to tissue growth in Bioen-OSMOSE. The net energy rate dome-shaped curve (in red) conforms to the OCLTT theory and the principle of TPC. Food shortage impacts ingested energy and downstream fluxes. Hypoxia impacts mobilized energy and downstream fluxes. The maximum of the net energy rate (red curve) is called T_{opt} hereafter.

2017, Lefevre *et al.*, 2018]. In addition, the maintenance rate also increases with the temperature $T(i, t)$ experienced by individuals [Gillooly *et al.*, 2002] and can be described as

$$E_m(i, t) = C_m w(i, t)^\beta \varphi_m(T(i, t))$$

with C_m the mass-specific maintenance rate and φ_m the Arrhenius function describing the effect of temperature on E_m , defined as:

$$\varphi_m(T(i, t)) = e^{\frac{-\varepsilon_m}{k_B T}}$$

with ε_m the activation energy for maintenance rate increase with temperature.

2.3.3 New tissue production: somatic and gonadic growth

The net energy available for new tissues production E_P is the difference between mobilized energy E_M and maintenance E_m , defined as follows:

$$E_P(i, t) = E_M(i, t) - E_m(i, t)$$

The net energy E_P contributes to the production of new tissues with a proportion ρ being allocated to the gonadic compartment $g(i, t)$ and a proportion $1 - \rho$ allocated to the somatic one $w(i, t)$. This proportion depends on sexual maturity status $m(i, t)$ of the schools' individuals and their somatic mass $w(i, t)$. Before sexual maturation, i.e., when $m(i, t) = 0$, is equal to 0 and, after maturation, i.e., when $m(i, t) = 1$, it is defined such that the annual mean gonado-somatic index of individuals $\frac{g(i, t)}{w(i, t)}$ is constant throughout their adult life-stage and equal to its genetically coded value $r(i)$ [Boukal *et al.*, 2014, Lester *et al.*, 2004, Quince *et al.*, 2008]:

$$\rho(i, t) = m(i, t) \frac{r(i)}{\eta \overline{E_P}(i)} w(i, t) \quad (2.1)$$

where

$$\overline{E_P}(i) = \frac{\Delta t}{a(i, t)} \sum_{t=0}^{t=a(i, t)/\Delta t} E_P(i, t')$$

is the average net energy available per time step to individuals of school i since their birth, with Δt being the duration of a time step. Equation (2.1) differs from a deterministic continuous time version of the same model [Boukal *et al.*, 2014, Lester *et al.*, 2004, Quince *et al.*, 2008] where the current net energy $E_P(i, t)$ would be used instead of the average $\overline{E_P}(i)$. The averaging in a stochastic discrete time individual-based model such as EV-OSMOSE insures a smooth increase of proportion ρ as individuals grow by dampening strong variations in $E_P(i, t)$ and thus in $\rho(i, t)$ due to the stochasticity of prey encounter and hence of ingested energy $I(i, t)$.

According to the definition of ρ , the net energy E_P is thus fully allocated to somatic growth before maturation and it is shared between somatic and gonadic growth after, and the proportion ρ allocated to gonads increases with mass [Boukal *et al.*, 2014], which limits somatic growth as individuals become bigger. However, in case mobilized energy E_M cannot fully cover maintenance E_m , i.e. when $E_P < 0$, new tissue production is not possible and the gonadic compartment $g(i, t)$ can be resorbed to provide energy for sustaining maintenance.

Somatic growth is then defined as follows:

$$\frac{dw}{dt}(i, t) = \begin{cases} (1 - \rho(i, t)) E_P(i, t) & \text{if } E_P \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

and gonadic growth as:

$$\frac{dg}{dt}(i, t) = \begin{cases} \eta\rho(i, t)E_P(i, t) & \text{if } E_P \geq 0 \\ \eta E_P(i, t) & \text{if } -g(i, t) \leq \eta E_P(i, t) < 0 \\ -g(i, t) & \text{if } \eta E_P(i, t) < -g(i, t) \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

where η is the ratio of energy density between somatic and gonadic tissues, and the second and third expressions account for maintenance coverage by energy reserves contained in gonads. In the former case, gonads' energy can fully cover maintenance costs but in the latter it cannot, so that individuals undergo energetic starvation and incur additional starvation mortality (see section 5 Mortality for more details).

Equation (2.2) mechanistically describes somatic mass increment at each time step. The length of an individual of school at time is then obtained from the length-mass allometric relationship:

$$L(i, t) = kw(i, t)^\alpha$$

where k and α are allometric parameters.

2.3.4 Maturation

Age and size at maturation vary strongly between individuals due to phenotypic plasticity. This plasticity in maturation is modeled by a deterministic linear maturation reaction norm (LMRN) that represents all the age-length combinations at which an individual can become mature [Stearns, 1992, Stearns and Koella, 1986]. In this framework, individuals become sexually mature when their growth trajectory in term of body length intersects the LMRN, so that the maturity status of individuals of school at time step is then described as:

$$m(i, t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } L(i, t) < m_0(i) + m_1(i)a(i, t) \text{ (immature)} \\ 1 & \text{if } L(i, t) \geq m_0(i) + m_1(i)a(i, t) \text{ (mature)} \end{cases}$$

with $m_0(i)$ and $m_1(i)$ the intercept and slope of the LMRN, respectively.

2.3.5 Reproduction

Mature individuals spawn during the breeding season, which occurs when successive time steps t have a spawning seasonality value $sp(t)$ (expressed as a fraction of spawning activity per time step and summing to 1 over one year) above 0. At the first time step of the breeding season, all the energy contained in the gonadic compartment $g(i, t)$ of individuals in school i is used to produce eggs. The sex-ratio is assumed to be 1 for 1 for all species and the number of eggs produced by school i for the whole breeding season is defined as follows:

$$N_{eggs}(i, t) = N(i, t) \frac{g(i, t)}{2w_{egg}}$$

with w_{egg} the weight of an egg. The pool $g(i, t)$ is then set to 0 and can start growing again (equation (2.3)) at the next time steps in view of the next spawning season. Then, the total number of eggs produced by the species $s(i)$ for the breeding season is obtained as

$$N_{eggs_{tot}} = \sum_{j \vee s(j)=s(i)} N_{eggs}(j, t)$$

At each time step t of the breeding season, N_s new schools are produced by species $s(i)$, with the number of eggs, and thus individuals, per new school i' calculated as follows:

$$N(i', t) = sp(t) \times \frac{N_{eggs_{tot}}}{N_s}$$

with age of offspring set to 0 ($a(i', t) = 0$), their somatic weight set to the weight of an egg ($w(i', t) = w_{egg}$) and their gonadic weight set to 0 ($g(i, t) = 0$). The new schools are released randomly depending on the specific larvae habitat map.

2.3.6 Mortality

At each time step, a school experiences several mortality sources. The total mortality of a school i is the sum of predation mortality caused by other schools, foraging mortality, starvation mortality, fishing mortality and diverse other natural mortalities (i.e. senescence, diseases, and non-explicitly modeled predators). Within each time step, the different mortality sources impact a school i in a random order so as to simulate the simultaneous nature of these processes.

The mortality induced by predation emerges from the energy uptake process previously described (see Section 2.3.1) and thus is an explicit stochastic size-dependent process depending on the spatial co-occurrence between predators and preys. The predation mortality experienced by school i is simply the sum of biomass losses due to the ingestion of all predator schools j present in the same grid cell $c(i, t)$ at time step t and with adequate minimum and maximum predator to prey size ratios ($R_{min}(s(j))$ and $R_{max}(s(j))$):

$$\frac{dB}{dt} = \sum_j \frac{\gamma(s(j), s(i))B(i, t)}{P(j, t)} I(j, t)$$

with

$$j \in \left(j \vee (c(j, t) = c(i, t)) \left(\frac{L(i, t)}{R_{max}(i)} \leq L(j, t) \leq \frac{L(i, t)}{R_{min}(i)} \right) \right)$$

where the ratio $\frac{\gamma(s(j), s(i))B(i, t)}{P(j, t)}$ represents the fact that predators prey on various prey schools according to their relative accessible abundance. Change in the number of individuals of school due to predation during time step is then given by:

$$N(i, t + \Delta t) = N(i, t) \left(1 - \sum_j \frac{\gamma(s(j), s(i))}{P(j, t)} I(j, t) \right)$$

Organisms face a trade-off between mortality and foraging activity [Mangel, 2003] because more active foraging implies a higher exposure to predation, more unfavorable condition encounters (e.g. diseases) and/or increased oxidative stress. Assuming that variation in mass-specific maximum ingestion rate I_{max} results from variation in foraging activity, this trade-off is modeled by including a foraging mortality that increases with I_{max} and thus when foraging activity is more intense. The instantaneous foraging mortality rate experienced by school is defined as follows:

$$M_f(i) = \mu_f I_{max}(i)$$

with μ_f a conversion coefficient from foraging activity to mortality that measures the trade-off's strength. Change in the number of individuals in school due to foraging mortality during time step is then obtained as:

$$N(i, t + \Delta t) = N(i, t) e^{-M_f(i)\Delta t}$$

Starvation occurs when an individual cannot cover its maintenance needs, i.e. when net energy is negative, even by drawing energy from its gonadic reserves, i.e. when (see Section 2.3.3 for details). In this case, schools undergo a decrease in biomass equaling the energetic deficit after accounting for the energy reserves contained in the gonadic compartment:

$$B(i, t + \Delta t) = B(i, t) - N(i, t) \left(\|E_P(i, t)\| - \frac{g(i, t)}{\eta} \right) \text{ if } \eta E_P(i, t) < -g(i, t)$$

so that change in the number of individuals of school i due to energetic starvation during time step t is then given by:

$$N(i, t + \Delta t) = N(i, t) \times \left(1 - \frac{\|E_P(i, t)\| - \frac{g(i, t)}{\eta}}{w(i, t)} \right) \text{ if } \eta E_P(i, t) < -g(i, t)$$

Starvation mortality at the time step $t + \Delta t$ relies on the net energy amount of time step t . During the first time step of a school, i.e. at eggs life stage, the school doesn't feed to model the energy provision yolk reserve. Then, starvation does not occur at the first and second time step as starvation at the second step time relies on first time step.

Fig. 2.3: Scheme for the functional response

EVO-OSMOSE ODD DESCRIPTION

The present section contains all the necessary information and guidelines to help understand the principles and assumptions of the Evolutionary version (EVO-OSMOSE) version of the OSMOSE model, apply it to a specific case study and run simulations for addressing specific issues.

3.1 Design concepts

3.1.1 Basic principles

EV-OSMOSE relies on a number of well-established concepts and theories and combines them in an original way to describe marine fish biodiversity and its dynamics from the intra-specific, genetic and phenotypic variability, to the inter-specific, taxonomic and trait-based level. Previous multi-species models of fish communities have been devised to project interspecific biodiversity trajectories under various scenarios considering only ecological dynamics. However, fish populations may also adapt to natural and anthropogenic pressures via phenotypic plasticity and/or evolutionary changes, leading to modifications in their physiology and life-history that could either mitigate or worsen the consequences of these pressures. EV-OSMOSE has been precisely developed to account for plastic and evolutionary dynamics in fish biodiversity projections by introducing the following elements to the existing OSMOSE model.

EV-OSMOSE describes explicitly mendelian inheritance of quantitative traits determined by polygenic genotypes according to quantitative genetics principles. These genotypes are composed of a finite number of loci and alleles per locus with effects of heterogeneous amplitude [Soularue and Kremer, 2012], which allows accounting realistically for both adaptive and neutral (genetic drift) evolutionary changes induced by natural and anthropogenic selective pressures. Genetically determined quantitative traits affect individuals' bioenergetics and sexual maturation processes, which are described with a bioenergetic submodel.

3.1.2 Emergence

Phenotypic values of schools' evolving traits- maximum ingestion rate I_{max} , gonado-somatic index r , intercept and slope of the maturation reaction norm m_0 and m_1 - are entirely determined by their genotype and randomly drawn expression noise. In contrast, other individual variables or traits at higher integrative levels of organization (hereafter named "emerging variables": somatic mass $w(i, t)$, length $L(i, t)$, gonadic mass $g(i, t)$ and thus fecundity $N_{eggs}(i, t)$, maturation age $a_m(i)$ and somatic mass or length at maturation $w_m(i)$ and $L_m(i)$) as well as starvation mortality emerge from the combination of evolving traits' values, energy intake from size-based opportunistic predation and physiological or plastic responses of bioenergetics to experienced sea water temperature and dissolved oxygen concentration (Figure 2).

Fig. 3.1: Ev-OSMOSE processes describing trait variations from loci to population level (pink) and the causes impacting trait values (blue).

3.2 Initialization

For each species, the initial pool of alleles present in the population for each functional or neutral locus is randomly drawn from a prescribed distribution (see [Section 3.3.1](#)). The system starts with no schools in the domain and eggs are released for every species during the specific reproductive season time step during a defined seeding period. The eggs are grouped in super-individuals, representing schools that are distributed spatially according to their habitat maps. For each school, a diploid genotype is randomly drawn from the functional and neutral pools of alleles at each locus.

For a given species, the seeding process stops when there is at least one mature individual in the population. If the mature part of the population collapses before the end of the seeding period, the seeding process is resumed (see maturation description in [Section 2.3.4](#)). Seeding ceases definitely at the end of the defined period. If a simulation is stopped before the end of the seeding period, the randomly drawn initial pools of functional and neutral alleles need to be saved as state variables in addition to those described in [Section 1.2](#) in order to be able to restart the ecosystem dynamics from the stopping time step.

3.3 Submodels

The genetic sub-model introduces a source of intra-specific variability of quantitative traits in OSMOSE, through additive genetic variance $\sigma_{A,Z}^2$ and expression variance $\sigma_{e,Z}^2$ and parental gene inheritance. The individuals are considered diploid hermaphrodites, i.e. without differentiation between males and females, the model being based on female life history. The genotypic values of the four heritable traits—maximum mass-specific ingestion rate I_{max} , gonado-somatic index r , intercept and slope of linear maturation reaction (m_0 and m_1 , respectively) norm—result from the expression of the corresponding functional loci. Neutral loci have no effect on individuals' phenotype: their evolution is the result of random drift. Hereafter, the genetic sub-model is described for any of the four evolving traits, generically denoted Z .

3.3.1 Genetic structure

The genetic structure is described by a polygenic multi-allelic model with finite numbers of loci and alleles for both the functional and neutral parts of the genome. The value of trait Z thus results from the expression of l_Z functional loci, each of which has a pool of $n_{Z,l}$ (with $l \in [1, 2, \dots, l_Z]$) possible alleles in the initial population characterized by their allelic value $A_{Z,l,k}$ (with $k \in [1, 2, \dots, n_{Z,l}]$).

Following classical quantitative genetics [[Lynch et al., 1998](#)], we assume that the genotypic values $G_Z(i)$ of trait Z in the population follow initially a normal distribution:

$$N(\overline{G_Z}(0), \sigma_{A,Z}^2(0))$$

with $\overline{G_Z}(0)$ the initial genotypic mean and $\sigma_{A,Z}^2(0)$ the initial additive genetic variance. It follows (see justification in the next section) that the allelic values $A_{Z,l,k}$ of the $n_{Z,l}$ alleles of locus l initially present in the population are randomly drawn from a normal distribution $N\left(0, \frac{\sigma_{A,Z}^2(0)}{2l_Z}\right)$ [[Soularue and Kremer, 2012](#)]. This allelic model defines allelic values as deviations around the initial genotypic mean $\overline{G_Z}(0)$ of the population and allows for heterogeneous allelic values across loci coding for the same trait, many of them with minor effects and a few ones with major effects.

Similarly, the neutral part of the genome is described by l_b neutral loci, each of which has a pool of $n_{b,l}$ (with $l \in [1, 2, \dots, l_b]$) possible alleles in the initial population characterized by their allelic identity $b_{l,k}$ (with $k \in [1, 2, \dots, n_{b,l}]$) with no effect of evolving trait values. The allelic identities $b_{l,k}$ of the alleles of locus l initially present in the population are randomly drawn from a discrete uniform distribution with probability mass function $\frac{1}{n_{b,l}}$.

3.3.2 Traits' genetic determinism and expression

The two alleles $A_{Z,l,k1}(i)$ and $A_{Z,l,k2}(i)$ at a functional locus l ($l \in [1, 2, \dots, l_Z]$) coding for trait $Z(i)$ of diploid individual i can each take one allelic value among the $n_{Z,l}$ versions possible in the population. Alleles act additively at and between loci. Since allelic values describe deviations around the mean genotypic value of trait Z , the genotype value $G_Z(i)$ for trait $Z(i)$ in school i is thus the sum of the initial genotypic mean $\overline{G_Z}(0)$ of the trait for the population and of the two allelic values $A_{Z,l,k}$ at each locus l coding for the trait of interest:

$$G_Z(i) = \overline{G_Z}(0) + \sum_{l=1}^{l=l_Z} (A_{Z,l,k1} + A_{Z,l,k2})$$

Given the normal distribution additive property and that the initial distributions $N\left(0, \frac{\sigma_{A,Z}^2(0)}{2l_Z}\right)$ of allelic values in the population are independent between loci, the initial distribution of genotypic values $G_Z(i)$ in the population thus follows a normal distribution $N(\overline{G_Z}(0), \sigma_{A,Z}^2(0))$. At later time steps t , the processes of selection, drift and inheritance will modify this distribution in terms of its mean $\overline{G_Z}(t)$ and its variance $\sigma_{A,Z}^2(t)$ but also potentially in terms of its shape as it is not constrained to stay normally distributed.

In EV-OSMOSE, part of the phenotypic expression of emerging variables (e.g. somatic mass $w(i, t)$, gonadic mass $g(i, t)$, length at maturation $L_m(i)$) is emerging from the bioenergetic responses to conditions faced by an individual: the available food, the temperature and the oxygen concentration in the environment during the entire individual life cycle. In contrast, the four evolving traits (maximum mass-specific ingestion rate I_{max} , gonado-somatic index r , intercept and slope of linear maturation reaction norm, m_0 and m_1) describe underlying individual characteristics whose phenotypic expression does not depend on these “macro-environmental” conditions. Yet, the phenotypic expression of evolving traits will also be affected by dominance and recessivity of alleles at the same locus and epistasis between loci, which are not modeled explicitly in the above genetic model, as well as by “micro-environmental” variations capturing the potentially unaccounted effects of individuals' internal environment or external micro-environment [Lynch *et al.*, 1998]. These sources of phenotypic variability for evolving trait are implicitly represented by an expression noise $e_Z(i)$ randomly drawn from a normal distribution $N(0, \sigma_{e,Z}^2)$ at the individual's birth and added to the genotypic value of its trait Z . The phenotypic value of evolving trait z for individual i is then:

$$Z(i) = G_Z(i) + e_Z(i)$$

3.3.3 Genetic inheritance

Both functional and neutral loci follow Mendelian inheritance under sexual reproduction. Reproduction is panmictic, which means that all sexually mature individuals can contribute to mating pairs of parents irrespective of their location and phenotype. When a new school is created during the breeding season (see section Reproduction), its two parents are randomly drawn from a multinomial distribution $M(2, p(t'))$ for 2 trials with a probability vector $p(t')$ composed of as many elements $p_i(t')$ as there are schools in the population. The i^{th} element of $p_i(t')$ is defined as the relative fecundity of school i in the population at the initial time step of the breeding season t :

$$p_i(t') = \frac{N_{eggs}(i, t)}{\sum_{j \vee s(j)=s(i)} N_{eggs}(j, t')}$$

with $N_{eggs}(i, t)$ the fecundity of school i and $\sum_{j \vee s(j)=s(i)} N_{eggs}(j, t')$ the total fecundity of the species $s(i)$ population at the initial time step of the breeding season t .

For each selected parental school, haploid gametes are assembled by randomly drawing one of the two alleles at each locus to represent allelic segregation during meiosis. This is done under the assumption of no linkage between loci, i.e. independence between loci, so that alleles recombine freely. New schools receive at each functional and neutral locus one allele from both chosen parents by randomly picking a haploid gamete for each of them.

GETTING STARTED

In this section, download and install instructions are provided.

4.1 Setup of the Osmose environment

4.1.1 Download Java

Since Osmose numerical JAVA core is coded in JAVA, Java need to be installed. Beforehand, let us clarify some of the acronyms regarding the Java technologies.

JVM: Java Virtual Machine. It is a set of software programs that interprets the Java byte code.

JRE: Java Runtime Environment. It is a kit distributed by Sun to execute Java programs. A JRE provides a JVM and some basic Java libraries. **A JRE is needed to run Osmose.** It can be downloaded from <https://www.java.com/fr/download/>.

JDK or SDK: Java (or Software) Development Kit bound to the programmer. It provides a JRE, a compiler, useful programs, examples and the source of the API (Application Programming Interface: some standard libraries). **A JDK is needed in order to modify the Osmose Java code.**

4.1.2 Download R

The Osmose-Java core is embedded in an Osmose-R package, which allows to pre-process, run and post-process Osmose outputs. Therefore, it is strongly advised that R be installed. Download instructions are available for [Windows](#), [Linux](#) and [Mac Os X](#).

It is also recommended to install the RStudio GUI (<https://rstudio.com/>).

4.1.3 Defining the Osmose target directory

Since Osmose version 3.3.4, Java executables and demo configuration files have been moved out of the R build to meet CRAN requirements on size package. These files are now downloaded from the Internet and moved to a local directory.

By default, a temporary directory is used; but in this case, the Java code will be downloaded at each new session. To define a directory where to put these downloads, the user need to edit or create a `~/.Renviron` file and to define the `OSMOSE_DIR` environment variable. More defined can be found on the [Osmose-R CRAN page](#)

4.2 Installing Osmose

The Osmose model is provided as a combination of a Java numerical core (referred to as Osmose-Java), associated with an Osmose R package (referred to as Osmose-R). The code is stored in two GitHub directories, a public one (<https://github.com/osmose-model/osmose>) and a private one (for developers only, <https://github.com/osmose-model/osmose-private>). There are several ways to install the Osmose model.

4.2.1 CRAN

The Osmose version on the `master` branch of the public repository is consistent with the most recent version of the package that is submitted to the CRAN. To install this version, open a R session and type `install.packages("osmose")`

4.2.2 Manual install

In order to use the development version of the Osmose model, it must be installed manually

Install from source files

The first way is to clone or download the source code and to install the code manually. To clone the directory, type in a Terminal:

To clone the Osmose repository:

```
# using HTTPS:
git clone https://github.com/osmose-model/osmose-private.git

# using SSH
git clone git@github.com:osmose-model/osmose-private.git
```

When a new version of the code is released, it can be updated as follows:

```
git pull
```

Note: When using the SSH, it is necessary to generate a RSA key that will connect the computer and the remote repository (see [Github Help](#) for details)

When the code has been downloaded, it must be installed as follows:

```
R CMD INSTALL osmose
```

Warning: The code must be reinstalled after each upgrade

Using devtools or RStudio

The Osmose package can also be by using the devtools R package or RStudio.

devtools

Open a R session and type the following lines:

```
library("devtools")
install_github("osmose-model/osmose")
```

RStudio

To install Osmose using RStudio, click on the *File* → *New Project* menu and open the *Version Control* → *Git* menu. Set the package URL (<https://github.com/osmose-model/osmose-private.git>). When the project is opened, click on the *Build & Reload* button to install the package.

4.3 Installing NetCDF library (Osmose >= 4.3)

Since Osmose 4.3.0, the Java library that manages input/outputs of NetCDF files requires the external NetCDF C library.

4.3.1 Mac Os X

To install the library on a Mac Os system, open a Terminal and type:

```
sudo port install netcdf4
```

4.3.2 Linux

To install the library on a Linux system, open a Terminal and type:

```
sudo apt-get install netcdf4
```

4.3.3 Windows

To install the library on a Windows system, download the pre-built libraries in [Unidata website](#)

4.4 Code architecture

4.4.1 Osmose <= 4.2.0

For Osmose <= 4.2.0, the directory contains the following folders, related to the R package

- The `inst/java` contains the Osmose Java core, provided as `.jar`.
- The `java` directory contains the Osmose Java source files associated with the `.jar` files.

- The R folder contains the R functions (pre/post processing tools, call to the JAVA core, etc.)
- The data-raw directory contains input files that can be used to run the model for the first time.
- The man and vignettes directories contain help files.

4.4.2 Osmose >= 4.3.0

For Osmose >= 4.3.0, the directory also contains the Java source files and compilation tools of the Osmose-Java core:

- The src directory contains the Java source files of the current Osmose version.
- The .xml files are Maven compilation files.
- The local directory contains external Java libraries needed by Osmose

4.5 Installation of the calibration library

The parameters of the Osmose model must be calibrated for each configuration. This is achieved by using the `calibrar` library.

The library is stored in GitHub (<https://github.com/roliveros-ramos/calibrar.git>) and can be installed following the same methods as described in Section 4.2, after changing the URL address.

4.6 (Optional) Compiling Osmose-Java

The compilation of Osmose-Java is not necessary to run Osmose, since Java executables are provided in the package. However, if the user wants to edit and recompile the Osmose-Java core, instructions are provided below.

4.6.1 Netbeans (Osmose <= 4.2.0)

Up to version 4.2.2, the only way to compile the Osmose Java core is by using the integrated development environment (IDE) Netbeans (<https://netbeans.org/downloads/>)

Note: It is highly advised to install together the JDK and the Netbeans bundle: <https://www.oracle.com/technetwork/java/javase/downloads/jdk-netbeans-jsp-3413139-esa.html>

The modification of the Java code is done as follows:

- Unzip one of the .zip file of the `osmose/java` directory
- Open Netbeans
- Click on *Open a project*
- Select the folder that has been extracted (should have a coffee cup icon)
- Edit the code
- Clean and build the project by pressing *Macj + F11*

This new .jar file can be used in the `run_osmose` function of the Osmose R package.

4.6.2 Maven (Osmose \geq 4.3.0)

From version 4.3.0, the code can be compiled independently of the Netbeans IDE by using the Apache Maven software project management and comprehension tool (<https://maven.apache.org/index.html>). When Maven is installed:

- Unzip one of the .zip file of the osmose/java directory
- Navigate to the directory via the Terminal (Linux/Mac) or Cmd (Windows) panel.
- Type `mvn install`

The sources will be built in the *target* directory.

Note: Maven projects can also be built with Netbeans, Eclipse or Visual Studio

4.7 Running the test configuration

To run the test configuration, launch R and type the following:

```
rm(list=ls())
getwd()

library(osmose)

demo = osmose_demo(path = "./", config="eec_4.3.0")

print(demo$config_file)
print(demo$extra_args)

# run the osmose java core
run_osmose(demo$config_file, parameters=demo$extra_args, force=TRUE)

# read the osmose outputs
data = read_osmose(demo$output_dir)

# plot the outputs
png(file="astart/_static/osmose_ref_conf.png")
plot(data)
```

You should obtain the following figure:

Fig. 4.1: Outputs of the reference configuration

OSMOSE MODEL

In this section, a detailed description of the Osmose model is provided.

5.1 Grid

The grid defines the geographical extent of the simulated domain and the spatial discretization.

5.1.1 Osmose \leq 4.1.0

In Osmose versions prior to 4.1.0, there were several ways to define the Osmose grid, depending on the input format of resource variables. This was controlled by using the `grid.java.classname` parameter.

`fr.ird.osmose.grid.NcGrid.java`

The easiest way to define an Osmose grid is via a NetCDF file, containing the geographical coordinates and a land/sea mask. It is parameterized as follows:

Table 5.1: Parameters for the `NcGrid.java` class

<code>grid.netcdf.file</code>	Name of the NetCDF file
<code>grid.var.lat</code>	Name of the latitude variable
<code>grid.var.lon</code>	Name of the longitude variable
<code>grid.var.mask</code>	Name of the mask variable

Points are considered as masked when the `mask` values is less equal than 0.

`fr.ird.osmose.grid.ECO3MGrid.java`

The `ECO3MGrid.java` class is very similar to `NcGrid.java`, excepts it has an additional parameter:

Table 5.2: Parameters for the `ECO3MGrid.java` class

<code>grid.stride</code>	Number of aggregation points
--------------------------	------------------------------

This parameter defines the number of input cells that will be aggregated together to make one osmose cell. For instance, a value of 4 implies that 16 cells of Eco3M grid will be used to make one cell of the Osmose model.

Note that the input values are expected to be double.

fr.ird.osmose.grid.BFMGrid.java

It is the same as ECO3MGrid.java, except that the input values of longitude, latitude and mask are expected to be float.

fr.ird.osmose.grid.OriginalGrid

Historically OSMOSE allows to define a regular grid, given a few parameters. Even though it is preferable to use the NetCDF grid definition, here is how a regular grid can be defined:

Table 5.3: Parameters for the ECO3MGrid.java class

grid.ncolumn	Number of longitudes
grid.nline	Number of latitudes
grid.lowright.lat	Lower right latitude
grid.lowright.lon	Lower right longitude
grid.upleft.lat	Upper left latitude
grid.upleft.lon	Upper right latitude
grid.mask.file	CSV containing the land-sea mask

The mask file is a CSV with `ncolumn` and `nline`. Land takes the value `-99`, and ocean cell are defined by a `0`. Here is an example of a CSV mask file for a 4x4 grid:

Note: The `grid.ncolumn` and `grid.nline` have been renamed to `grid.nlon` and `grid.nlat` in version 3.3.3

Table 5.4: Example of a 4x4 grid file

0	0	0	0
0	0	0	-99
0	0	-99	-99
0	0	-99	-99

5.1.2 Osmose >= 4.2.0

From Osmose 4.2.0, only the `NcGrid.java` class has been kept.

Danger: Therefore, old configurations will need pre-processing in order to run with the most recent Osmose versions

5.1.3 Osmose >= 4.3.0

In Osmose >= 4.3, NaN will be considered as land points. Therefore, resource files with filled values over land can be used as a mask file.

Furthermore, an additional optional parameter has been added, `grid.var.surf`, which provides the name of the cell surface variable (which must be defined in m^2). If not provided, cell surfaces will be reconstructed from longitude and latitude coordinates.

5.2 Biotic resources

Biotic resources such as phytoplankton and zooplankton are not explicitly modelled in Osmose but are essential to take into account as they constitute the base of the trophic chain. They are considered as an input of the model, spatially explicit and varying with time.

In this section, the way LTL biotic resources are defined is described

5.2.1 Osmose \leq 4.2.0

In the Osmose versions prior to 4.2.0, the biotic resources were defined as follows:

Table 5.5: List of parameters to define biotic resources (\leq 4.2.0)

plankton.name.plk#	Name of the plankton group.
plankton.TL.plk#	Trophic level of the plankton group.
plankton.size.min.plk#	Minimum size of the organisms in the plankton group (centimeters).
plankton.size.max.plk#	Maximum size of the organisms in the plankton group (centimeters).
plankton.accessibility2fish.plk#	Fraction of the plankton biomass that is accessible to the fish, ranging from zero to one.

The `plankton.accessibility2fish.plk#` parameter accounts for many biological processes that are not explicitly represented in Osmose and basically says that only a small fraction of the plankton in the water column is effectively available to the fish for preying upon. Plankton accessibility is generally completely unknown and, just like larval mortality, it should be estimated in the calibration process.

5.2.2 Osmose \geq 4.3.0

Since Osmose 4.3.0, plankton groups are defined using the same parameters, except that they have different names.

Table 5.6: List of parameters to define biotic resources (\geq 4.3.0)

species.name.sp#	Name of the plankton group.
species.TL.sp#	Trophic level of the plankton group.
species.size.min.sp#	Minimum size of the organisms in the plankton group (centimeters).
species.size.max.sp#	Maximum size of the organisms in the plankton group (centimeters).
species.accessibility2fish.sp#	Fraction of the plankton biomass that is accessible to the fish, ranging from zero to one.
species.type.sp#	Type of the species. Must be resource for biotic resources

An additional argument, `species.type.sp#`, must be defined and set to `resource` for biotic resources.

5.3 Background species

Background species have first been introduced in Osmose by [Fu *et al.*, 2017]. They can be viewed as an intermediary between focal species (i.e. species of interest, whose full life cycle is simulated) and lower trophic levels (plankton for instance). They differ from lower trophic levels since they can feed on focal species and be targeted by fisheries (since version 4.3)

They are available on Osmose since version 4.1.0, although their parameterization has changed in version 4.3.0.

5.3.1 Osmose <= 4.1.0

Background parameters in Osmose version 4.1.0 are parameterized as follows:

Table 5.7: Parameters for background species.

biomass.byDt.bySize.file.bkg#	CSV file containing the background species biomass by size class and by time step.
species.trophiclevel.bkg#	Array of trophic level (one for each size class)
species.name.bkg#	Name of the background species
species.length2weight.allometric.power.bkg#	Allometric factor for weight to length conversion
species.length2weight.condition.factor.bkg#	Allometric power for weight to length conversion
predation.accessibility.stage.threshold.bkg#	Threshold for accessibility matrix
predation.ingestion.rate.max.bkg#	I_{max} (grams of food per gram of fish and per year)
predation.predPrey.stage.threshold.bkg#	Age or size thresholds for predation/prey size ratios
predation.predPrey.sizeRatio.max.bkg#	Array of R_{max} values
predation.predPrey.sizeRatio.min.bkg#	Array of R_{min} values

The biomass provided in the CSV file will then be distributed over the domain using distribution maps (similar to the ones defined for focal species).

Table 5.8: Parameters for background species.

movement.bkgspecies.species.map#	Name of the background species to which the map is associated.
movement.bkgspecies.class.map#	Size class for which the map is associated.
movement.bkgspecies.season.map#	Time steps during which the map will be used
movement.bkgspecies.year.min.map#	Initial year when the map will be used
movement.bkgspecies.year.max.map#	Final year when the map will be used

Warning: For background species, the size classes are **fixed!**

Accessibility matrix

When using background species, the accessibility matrix must be changed accordingly. It must always have the following form:

	Focal (pred)	Background (pred)
Focal (prey)		
Background (prey)		
LTL (prey)		

Background biomass

Background species biomass is defined from a biomass time series (one per species and per size class) and by distribution maps. The distribution maps contain defines the distribution of the background species over space. They contain float values, which are normalize, so that the integral over space equals one:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{N_{cell}-1} D_k = 1$$

Before each time step, the background species biomass is reset by multiplying the biomass time series by the map distribution factor. Because of the normalisation, the spatially integrated biomass is equal to the biomass provided in the time-series.

5.3.2 Osmose >= 4.3.0

In Osmose version >= 4.3, background species are parameterized as follows:

Table 5.9: Parameters for background species ($\geq 4.3.0$)

Species parameters	
species.name.sp#	Name of the background species
species.type.sp#	Type of the background species. Must be background
species.length2weight.allometric.power.sp#	Allometric factor for weight to length conversion
species.length2weight.condition.factor.sp#	Allometric power for weight to length conversion
predation.efficacy.critical.sp#	Critical predation success (C_{SR})
predation.ingestion.rate.max.sp#	I_{max} (grams of food per gram of fish and per year)
predation.predPrey.stage.threshold.sp#	Age or size thresholds for predation/prey size ratios
predation.predPrey.sizeRatio.max.sp#	Array of R_{max} values
predation.predPrey.sizeRatio.min.sp#	Array of R_{min} values
Resource forcing parameters	
species.biomass.total.sp#	Total biomass for the given resource (will be distributed over the whole domain)
species.file.sp#	Regular expression defining the input files. Can be a file name.
species.file.caching.sp#	Resource caching method. Must be none, incremental or all (default).
Background species parameters	
species.nclass.sp#	Number of size classes.
species.trophiclevel.sp#	Array of trophic level (one value for each size class)
species.age.sp#	Array of school ages (one value per each size class)
species.length.sp#	Array of school lengths (one value for each size class)
species.size.proportion.sp#	Array of size proportion (one value for each size class)

The spatio-temporal distribution of background is now defined from a NetCDF file (see [Section 5.4](#)).

The distribution among size is now controlled by the `species.nclass.sp#` and `species.size.proportion.sp#` parameters.

Warning: At this time, the distribution among the size classes is constant over the entire simulation.

5.4 Resource forcing

5.4.1 Osmose $\leq 4.0.0$

In Osmose versions $\leq 4.0.0$, there were several ways to read the resource forcing files, depending on the value of the `ttl.java.classname` parameter.

ECO3M

If the class name is set equal to `fr.ird.osmose.ltl.LTLForcingECO3M` or `fr.ird.osmose.ltl.LTLFastForcingECO3M`, data values were read as follows.

Table 5.10: Eco3M resource parameters

<code>ltl.nstep</code>	Number of total time steps in the LTL files
<code>plankton.conversion2tons.plk#</code>	Conversion factor in tons
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.plankton.plk#</code>	Names of the Netcdf resource names
<code>ltl.netcdf.file.t#</code>	Names of the NetCDF files to read.
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.zlevel</code>	Name of the 3D depth variable
<code>grid.stride#</code>	Number of input cells that will be aggregated in an Osmose cell.
<code>ltl.integration.depth</code>	Maximum depth where to perform vertical integration

BFM

If the class name is set equal to `fr.ird.osmose.ltl.LTLForcingBFM` or `fr.ird.osmose.ltl.LTLFastForcingBFM`, data values were read as follows.

Table 5.11: BFM resource parameters

<code>ltl.nstep</code>	Number of time steps within a file.
<code>plankton.conversion2tons.plk#</code>	Conversion factor in tons
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.plankton.plk#</code>	Names of the Netcdf resource names
<code>ltl.netcdf.file.t#</code>	Names of the NetCDF files to read.
<code>ltl.netcdf.dim.ntime</code>	Number of time steps within a file
<code>grid.netcdf.file</code>	Name of the bathymetry file
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.zlevel</code>	Name of the 1D depth variable
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.bathy</code>	Name of the bathymetry variable
<code>ltl.integration.depth</code>	Maximum depth where to perform vertical integration

ROMS/PISCES

If the class name is set equal to `fr.ird.osmose.ltl.LTLForcingRomsPisces` or `fr.ird.osmose.ltl.LTLFastForcingRomsPisces`, data values were read as follows.

Table 5.12: ROMS/PISCES resource parameters

<code>ltl.nstep</code>	Number of time steps within a file.
<code>plankton.conversion2tons.plk#</code>	Conversion factor in tons
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.plankton.plk#</code>	Names of the Netcdf resource names
<code>ltl.netcdf.file.t#</code>	Names of the NetCDF files to read.
<code>ltl.netcdf.grid.file</code>	Name of the grid file
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.lon</code>	Name of the longitude variable
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.lat</code>	Name of the latitude variable
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.bathy</code>	Name of the bathymetry variable
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.csr</code>	Name of the CSR variable
<code>ltl.netcdf.var.hc</code>	Name of the Hc variable
<code>ltl.integration.depth</code>	Maximum depth where to perform vertical integration

Fast forcing

In the above configurations, Osmose processes the file to convert them into the right format. However, there is also the possibility to use a file already in the right format using the `fr.ird.osmose.ltl.LTLFastForcing` class.

Table 5.13: Fast forcing resource parameters

<code>ltl.nstep</code>	Number of time steps within a file.
<code>ltl.netcdf.file</code>	Name of the resource NetCDF file
<code>plankton.biomass.total.plk#</code>	Total biomass within the domain. If not found, reads value from NetCDF
<code>plankton.multiplier.plk#</code>	Multiplier of input biomass (default 1, used to run sensitivity experiments).

The netcdf file must contain a 4d variable `ltl_biomass`, whose dimensions are (time, ltl, lat, lon)

Danger: The order along the `ltl` dimension must be consistent with the order of definition of the plankton parameters.

Danger: With the fast forcing, the `plankton.conversion2tons.plk#` parameter is not used since data must be provided in tons!

5.4.2 Osmose 4.1.0 - 4.2.0

In versions 4.1.0 and 4.2.0, only the `FastForcing` method has been kept. However, it has been slightly improved. Now the model can take one NetCDF file per resource variable, and the variable in the NetCDF must match the `plankton.name.plk#` parameter. In this way, there is no more dependency on the order.

Table 5.14: Fast forcing resource parameters

<code>plankton.biomass.total.plk#</code>	Total biomass within the domain. If not found, reads value from NetCDF
<code>ltl.nstep</code>	Number of time steps within a file.
<code>ltl.netcdf.file.plk#</code>	Name of the resource NetCDF file (one for each resource)
<code>plankton.multiplier.plk#</code>	Multiplier of input biomass (default 1, used to run sensitivity experiments).

Danger: Resource species for which `plankton.biomass.total.plk#` is used should be defined last, i.e. their index # should be greater than those of the other species.

Danger: The resource files must be provided in tons! **The `plankton.conversion2tons.plk#` parameter is not used.

5.4.3 Osmose \geq 4.3.0

In the 4.3.0 version, the resource forcing remains similar to versions 4.1-4.2, with some changes in parameters.

Table 5.15: Fast forcing resource parameters

<code>species.biomass.total.sp#</code>	Total biomass for the given resource (will be distributed over the whole domain)
<code>species.file.sp#</code>	Regular expression defining the input files. Can be a file name.
<code>species.file.caching.sp#</code>	Resource caching method. Must be <code>none</code> , <code>incremental</code> or <code>all</code> (default).

If the `species.biomass.total.sp#` is not found, then the value will be read from the NetCDF file.

The `species.file.sp#` parameter can now take as an input regular expressions, which will allow to loop over all the files. The regular expressions must be defined in Java mode (see for instance XXX).

The `species.file.caching.sp#` defines how the input data will be read:

- In `all` mode, all the dataset is read at the first time step and stored into memory. *Should be used for climatological forcings for instance.*
- In `incremental` mode, each time a new time-step is read from file, it is stored in memory. Previous time-steps are kept in memory.
- In `none` mode, the data is read from file at each time-step. This mode is costly in term of runtime but light in memory since only one time-step is stored.

Note: In version 4.3.0, the resource forcing parameter also applies to background species.

ECONOMIC MODULE

In this section, information on the Economic Module OSMOSE-EC is provided.

6.1 Introduction

The economic model takes into account supply and demand dynamics. Supply depends mainly on fishing costs that are stock-dependent and technology-dependent. Demand is driven by the price that consumers are willing to pay and consumer preferences for different species and different size classes. Since evolutionary change impacts demographic changes within the fish population it is particularly interesting to study economic impacts given consumer preferences for size classes.

6.1.1 Costs

Based on [Tahvonen *et al.*, 2018], [Quaas *et al.*, 2018], [Lancker *et al.*, 2019]

Fishing costs depend on the availability of fish and the amount of fish harvested. We assume perfect selectivity with respect to species, but imperfect selectivity with respect to the size of species. Depending on the gear, larger or smaller fish of a species can be retained by the gear. The part of the population that could potentially be harvested is the accessible biomass. For example, with a trawl-like fishing net the probability of retainment increases with the size of the fish by a sigmoid pattern

$$q_{i,s}(\sigma_{i,t}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\omega_i (l_{i,s} - \sigma_{i,t})}}$$

with length of fish l_s in size class s , mesh size σ_t in year t and selectivity accuracy ω assumed to be constant. The total available (or accessible) biomass of a species i is therefore

$$B_{i,t} = \sum_s q_{i,s}(\sigma_{i,t}) w_{i,s} N_{i,s,t}$$

where $w_{i,s}$ is the weight of fish species i in size class s and $N_{i,s,t}$ is the number of fish in that size class in a given year.

The costs of harvesting fish increases with harvest and decreases when more fish are accessible.

$$C_{i,t} = c_{i,t} \frac{H_{i,t}}{B_{i,t}^{\chi_i}}$$

Here, $c_{i,t}$ are baseline harvesting costs that may increase over time (with increasing fuel prices) or decrease (with technological advancement), such that $c_{i,t} = c_{i,0} e^{\tau_i(t-t_0)}$ with trend τ_i . The parameter χ_i is the stock elasticity. When $\chi_i < 1$ the stock is hyperstable, meaning that at constant effort an increase in available biomass does not necessarily result in a higher harvest.

Fishermen's profit is the revenue from selling fish minus costs of harvesting.

$$\Pi_{i,t} = \sum_s p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t} - C_{i,t}$$

The profit margin is the fraction of profits with respect to revenues

$$\pi_{i,t} = \frac{\sum_s p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t} - C_{i,t}}{\sum_s p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t}}$$

6.1.2 Demand

Based on [Quaas and Requate, 2013], [Quaas *et al.*, 2016], [Quaas *et al.*, 2018], [Groeneveld and Quaas, 2016], [Tahvonen *et al.*, 2018], [Lancker *et al.*, 2019]

Consumers have preferences for certain species but also size classes of fish. Yet when preferred species are rare, and thus expensive, consumers can shift their consumption towards more abundant species, depending on the elasticity of demand. The more elastic demand is, the easier it is to substitute. The same holds for different size classes of fish, where demand is likely to be even more elastic - you would not pay an extremely high price for a bigger fish than for the same mass of small fishes.

The utility of fish consumption is

$$\nu_t = \left(\sum_{i=1}^I \alpha_i \left(\sum_{s=1}^S \beta_{is} h_{is}^{\frac{\mu_i-1}{\mu_i}} \right)^{\frac{\mu_i}{\mu_i-1} \frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} \right)^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}}$$

Here μ_i is the elasticity of substitution for different size classes of fish species i , σ is the elasticity of substitution between different species, $\beta_{i,s}$ are the constant consumer preferences for size classes and α_i are consumer preferences for species.

Consumers pay for fish consumption, therefore total utility is

$$u(\nu_t) = \begin{cases} \gamma \ln(\nu_t) - \sum_i \sum_s p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t} & \text{if } \eta = 1 \\ \gamma \frac{\eta}{\eta-1} \nu_t^{\frac{\eta-1}{\eta}} - \sum_i \sum_s p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t} & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

where γ is the total expenditure on fish when $\eta = 1$

Consumers maximise utility over the consumption of fish $h_{i,s,t}$ resulting in the inverse demand function

$$p_{i,s,t} = \gamma \left(\beta_{i,s} h_{i,s,t}^{-\frac{1}{\mu_i}} \right) \alpha_i \left(\sum_k \beta_{i,k} h_{i,k,t}^{\frac{\mu_i-1}{\mu_i}} \right)^{\frac{\mu_i}{\mu_i-1} \frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma} - 1} \nu_t^{\frac{1}{\sigma} - \frac{1}{\eta}}$$

6.1.3 Social optimum

In total, the utility derived from fish consumption is the benefit obtained from fish consumption of different species and size classes minus the costs needed for their extraction. Since individuals discount future utility (we prefer to have something today rather than tomorrow), the total net present value is

$$\begin{aligned} NPV &= u(\nu_t) + \Pi_{i,t} \\ &= \sum_{t=t_0}^{t_0+T} \delta^t \left(\left(\gamma \frac{\eta}{\eta-1} \nu_t^{\frac{\eta-1}{\eta}} - \sum_i \sum_s p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t} \right) - \left(\sum_i \sum_s p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t} - \sum_i C_{i,t} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{t=t_0}^{t_0+T} \delta^t \left(\gamma \frac{\eta}{\eta-1} \nu_t^{\frac{\eta-1}{\eta}} - \sum_i C_{i,t} \right) \end{aligned}$$

with discount factor δ . The first term is the consumers' utility and the last term is fishermen's profit.

A social planner, that accounts for consumer and producer surplus, would maximise this net present value over future control variables in the fishery, here future harvests and mesh sizes.

6.2 Calibration

We estimate parameters of the cost function given catch, accessible biomass and profitability data. Species and size class preferences are estimated using the inverse demand function and assuming market equilibrium.

6.2.1 Cost parameter estimation

Rearranging the definition of the profit margin we get

$$\ln(1 - \pi_{i,t}) \ln \left(\frac{\sum_s p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t}}{H_{i,t}} \right) = \ln(c_{i0}) - \chi_i \ln(B_{it}) + \tau_i t,$$

and we can estimate baseline costs $c_{i,0}$, stock elasticity χ_i and the time trend on fishing costs τ_i .

6.2.2 Demand parameter estimation

Rearranging the inverse demand function we get

$$p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t}^{\frac{1}{\mu_i}} = \beta_{i,s} \sum_j p_{i,j,t} h_{i,j,t}^{\frac{1}{\mu_i}}$$

and

$$\mathcal{P}_{i,t} \mathcal{H}_{i,t}^{\frac{1}{\sigma}} = \alpha_i \sum_j \mathcal{P}_{j,t} \mathcal{H}_{j,t}^{\frac{1}{\sigma}}$$

with $\mathcal{P}_{i,t} := \sum_k \frac{p_{i,k,t} h_{i,k,t}^{\frac{1}{\mu_i}}}{\beta_{i,k}}$ and $\mathcal{H}_{i,t} := \left(\sum_k \beta_{i,k} h_{i,k,t}^{\frac{\mu_i-1}{\mu_i}} \right)^{\frac{\mu_i-\sigma}{\mu_i-1}}$ we can first estimate size preferences $\beta_{i,s}$ for each species and then species preferences α_i .

The elasticities of substitution between size classes μ_i and between species σ are either taken from the literature or assumed.

Furthermore, given ν_t as defined before and using

$$\ln \left(\sum_i \sum_s p_{i,s,t} h_{i,s,t} \right) = \ln(\gamma) + \frac{\eta-1}{\eta} \ln(\nu_t)$$

we estimate γ and η .

6.2.3 Data requirements

For the parameterisation we need

- profit margins π_{it} . If this is not available and the fishery has been operating at or close to open access conditions the profit margin is zero.
- prices per kg $p_{i,s,t}$

- the weight of individuals $w_{i,s}$ in kg
- the catchability $q_{i,s,t}$, the proportion of individuals in a size class that are retained in the net. Needs to be between 0 and 1. Alternatively one can fit the catchability to fishing mortalities $F_{i,s,t} = F_{i,t}^{max} q_{i,s,t}$.
- population numbers $N_{i,s,t}$
- instead of catchability and numbers it is possible to provide instead the harvest $h_{i,s,t}$ and the accessible biomass $B_{i,t}$

for species (i), size class (s) and year (t) as indicated.

6.3 Parameters

Short explanation of parameters

Table 6.1: Estimated parameters

$c_{i,0}$	baseline costs of harvesting in the year t_0 (usually 2020)
τ_i	exponential time trend (positive or negative) on costs of harvesting
χ_i	stock elasticity. If >1 the stock is hypersensitive: fishing costs decline fast with accessible biomass. If <1 the stock is hyperstable and fishing costs remain relatively constant with the available biomass
$\beta_{i,s}$	consumer preferences for different sizes (s) of each species (i). $\sum_s \beta_{i,s} = 1$
α_i	consumer preferences for different species (i). $\sum_i \alpha_i = 1$
η	elasticity of demand for fish
γ	weight of fish consumption in total utility. When $\eta = 1$ it is the total expenditure on fish

Table 6.2: Parameters from the literature

μ_i	elasticity of substitution between different sizes of a species (i). Higher values indicate easier substitutability
σ	elasticity of substitution between species of fish. Should be lower than μ_i since sizes are better substitutes than species.

6.4 Output

Total profit

Total revenue

Total costs

Future prices

Scenarios: change harvest ($H_{i,t}$), change distribution of harvest over size classes, delete time trend ($\tau_{i,t}=0$), see what happens when consumers prefer larger or smaller fish (change $\beta_{i,s}$)...

PRE/POST PROCESSING OF OSMOSE MODEL

In this section, the pre/post processing tools of the `osmose` package are presented

7.1 Library loading

```
require("osmose")  
  
ls("package:osmose")
```

```
Loading required package: osmose  
[1] "cacheManager"      "get_var"  
[3] "getVar"            "initialize_osmose"  
[5] "osmose_calib_demo" "osmose_demo"  
[7] "osmose_grid"       "osmose2R"  
[9] "read_osmose"       "readOsmoseConfiguration"  
[11] "report"            "run_osmose"  
[13] "runOsmose"         "update_maps"  
[15] "update_osmose"     "write_osmose"  
[17] "write.osmose"
```

7.2 Reading Osmose parameters

The loading of Osmose parameters is achieved by using the `read_osmose` function with an input argument providing the path of the main configuration file.

```
suppressMessages(require("osmose"))  
  
output.dir = file.path("rosmose", "_static")  
  
exampleFolder <- tempdir()  
demoPaths <- osmose_demo(path = exampleFolder, config = "eec_4.3.0")  
  
# load the Osmose configuration file  
osmConf = readOsmoseConfiguration(demoPaths$config_file)  
  
# Summarize the configuration  
summary(osmConf)
```

(continues on next page)

```

# extracting a particular configuration object
sim = get_var(osmConf, what="simulation")

# proper way to recover the season parameter (returns a vector of numeric)
movements = get_var(osmConf, what='movement')

# Plotting reproduction growth
png(filename = file.path(output.dir, 'species.png'))
plot(osmConf, what="species", species=0)

# Plotting reproduction seasonality
png(filename = file.path(output.dir, 'reproduction.png'))
plot(osmConf, what="reproduction", species=1)

# Plotting size range for predation

```

	Length	Class	Mode
osmose	2	-none-	list
mortality	4	-none-	list
simulation	7	-none-	list
fishing	1	-none-	list
movement	7	-none-	list
fisheries	9	-none-	list
predation	4	-none-	list
reproduction	1	-none-	list
species	17	-none-	list
grid	3	-none-	list
population	1	-none-	list
output	19	-none-	list

Furthermore, some parameters can be plotted for a given species. This is done as follows:

```

png(filename = file.path(output.dir, 'predation.png'))
plot(osmConf, what="predation", species=2)

```

7.3 Running the model

OSMOSE Java can be run from R by using the `run_osmose` function.

```

library("osmose")

# recover the reference configuration file
filename = system.file(package="osmose", "extdata", "master", "osm_all-parameters.csv")

# setting output directory
outdir = 'output'

# default run mode (java file in inst/java/)
run_osmose(input=filename, output=outdir)

```


Fig. 7.1: Growth parameters for species 0

Fig. 7.2: Reproduction seasonality for species 1

Fig. 7.3: Predation size range for species 2

By default, the OSMOSE Java included in the package is used. However, the user is free to use another build of the OSMOSE Java program as follows:

```
# Running Osmose by using another version of the .jar file.
jarfile = "/home/nbarrier/Modeles/osmose/svn-osmose/trunk/dist/osmose-trunk.jar"
run_osmose(osmose=jarfile, input=fileName,
           output=outdir, version="4")
```

Warning: The way the OSMOSE Java core is called has changed between versions 3 and 4. As a consequence, the user must be sure to properly set the `version` argument.

7.4 Reading outputs

The reading of outputs is achieved by using the `read_osmose` function:

```
library("osmose")

data = read_osmose(path='output')
```

The content of the data object can be obtained as follows:

```
names(data)
```

```
[1] "model"           "species"         "biomass"
[4] "abundance"      "mortality"       "meanTL"
[7] "meanTLCatch"    "biomassByTL"     "predatorPressure"
[10] "predPreyIni"    "dietMatrix"      "meanSize"
[13] "meanSizeCatch"  "SizeSpectrum"    "abundanceBySize"
[16] "biomassBySize"  "meanTLBySize"    "mortalityBySize"
[19] "dietMatrixBySize" "predatorPressureBySize" "abundanceByAge"
[22] "biomassByAge"   "meanSizeByAge"   "meanTLByAge"
[25] "mortalityByAge" "dietMatrixByAge"  "predatorPressureByAge"
[28] "abundanceByTL" "yieldByFishery"  "yield"
[31] "yieldN"         "yieldBySize"     "yieldNBySize"
[34] "yieldByAge"     "yieldNByAge"     "discards"
[37] "surveyBiomass"  "surveyAbundance" "surveyYield"
[40] "sizeMature"     "ageMature"       "ingestion"
[43] "ingestionTot"   "maintenance"     "meanEnet"
[46] "sizeInf"        "kappa"           "abundAge1"
[49] "ingestByAge"    "ingestBySize"    "kappaByAge"
[52] "kappaBySize"    "enetByAge"       "enetBySize"
[55] "maintenanceByAge" "maintenanceBySize" "meanWeightByAge"
[58] "meanWeightBySize" "meanWeightByWeight" "yieldByWeight"
[61] "yieldNByWeight"  "abundanceByWeight" "biomassByWeight"
[64] "yield.fishery0"  "yield.fishery1"   "yield.fishery2"
[67] "yield.fishery3"  "yield.fishery4"   "yield.fishery5"
[70] "yield.fishery6"  "yield.fishery7"   "yield.fishery8"
[73] "yield.fishery9"  "yield.fishery10"  "yield.fishery11"
[76] "yield.fishery12" "yield.fishery13"  "config"
```

Variables are accessed by using the `getVar` function, which allows to apply some operations prior to extraction (average over the replicates, conversion into a list or a matrix):

```
library("osmose")

getwd()
input.dir = file.path("eec_4.3.0", "output-PAPIER-trophic")
data = read_osmose(input.dir)

biom = get_var(data, "biomass")
class(biom)
dim(biom)
cat("\n")

# expected = TRUE if mean over replicate should be returned
# only works for data that inherits from array
biom = get_var(data, "biomass", expected=TRUE)
class(biom)
dim(biom)
cat("\n")

biom = get_var(data, "biomass", how="list")
class(biom)
names(biom)
cat(biom$OctopusVulgaris)
cat("\n")

biom = get_var(data, "dietMatrixByAge")
class(biom)
cat("\n")

biom = get_var(data, "dietMatrixByAge", how="list")
class(biom)
```

```
[1] "/home/barrier/Codes/osmose/git-osmose/doc"
[1] "osmose.biomass" "array"
[1] 30 14 1

[1] "matrix" "array"
[1] 30 14

[1] "list"
[1] "lesserSpottedDogfish" "redMullet" "pouting"
[4] "whiting" "poorCod" "cod"
[7] "dragonet" "sole" "plaice"
[10] "horseMackerel" "mackerel" "herring"
[13] "sardine" "squids"

[1] "osmose.dietMatrixByAge" "list"

[1] "list"
```

The first argument is the data object obtained by using the `read_osmose` function, while the second argument is the name of the variable to extract.

7.4.1 Reading NetCDF outputs

In the new Osmose version, the user has the possibility to save outputs as NetCDF (.nc) instead of CSV (.csv) files. **However, no function has been provided to automatically read all the Osmose NetCDF files.** Therefore, scripts must be written by the user, following the example shown below:

```
rm(list=ls())

library("ncdf4")

filename = file.path("rosnose", "_static",
                    "gogosm_mortalityRateDistribByAge-OctopusVulgaris_Simu0.nc")

print("@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@ fid")
fid = nc_open(filename)
print(fid)

print("@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@ vars")
var = fid$var
print(names(var))
mort = ncvar_get(fid, "mortality")

print("@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@ dims")
dims = fid$dim
print(names(dims))

print("@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@ mortality")
mcause = ncvar_get(fid, "mortality_cause")
attrs = ncatt_get(fid, "mortality_cause")
print(attrs)

print("@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@ age")
age = ncvar_get(fid, "Age")
print(age)
```

```
[1] "@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@@ fid"
File rosmose/_static/gogosm_mortalityRateDistribByAge-OctopusVulgaris_Simu0.nc (NC_
↪FORMAT_CLASSIC):

  1 variables (excluding dimension variables):
    float mortality[mortality_cause,Age,time]
      units:
        description: Predation (Mpred), Starvation (Mstarv), Other Natural mortality_
↪(Mnat), Fishing (F) & Out-of-domain (Z) mortality rates per time step of saving and_
↪per size class. Z is the total mortality for migratory fish outside the simulation_
↪grid. To get annual mortality rates, sum the mortality rates within one year.
        _FillValue: -99

  3 dimensions:
    time Size:12 *** is unlimited ***
      units: days since 0-1-1 0:0:0
      calendar: 360_day
      description: time ellapsed, in days, since the beginning of the simulation
```

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```

Age Size:25
mortality_cause Size:6
  mortality_cause0: PREDATION
  mortality_cause1: STARVATION
  mortality_cause2: ADDITIONAL
  mortality_cause3: FISHING
  mortality_cause4: OUT
  mortality_cause5: OXY
[1] "##### vars"
[1] "mortality"
[1] "##### dims"
[1] "time"          "Age"          "mortality_cause"
[1] "##### mortality"
$mortality_cause0
[1] "PREDATION"

$mortality_cause1
[1] "STARVATION"

$mortality_cause2
[1] "ADDITIONAL"

$mortality_cause3
[1] "FISHING"

$mortality_cause4
[1] "OUT"

$mortality_cause5
[1] "OXY"

[1] "##### age"
[1] 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24

```

7.5 Plotting outputs

Plotting Osmose outputs is achieved by calling the generic plot function on the `osmose` object, output by the `read_osmose` function. The function takes as argument the variable to be displayed (what argument). The species argument allows to specify the indexes of the species to display (cf. the `X` in the `species.name.spX` parameters).

```

library("osmose")

input.dir = file.path("eec_4.3.0", "output-PAPIER-trophic")
data = read_osmose(input.dir)

output.dir = file.path("rosmose", "_static")

test = get_var(data, "species")

png(file=file.path(output.dir, "biomass.png"))

```

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```

plot(data, what="biomass")

png(file=file.path(output.dir, "abundance.png"))
plot(data, what="abundance", species=c(0, 1, 2))

png(file=file.path(output.dir, "yield.png"))
plot(data, what="yield")

png(file=file.path(output.dir, "yieldN.png"))
plot(data, what="yieldN")

```

Hint: When several replicates are run, the uncertainty due to the stochastic mortality is displayed as a grey shading.

Warning: At this time, only these four variables can be plotted. However, more plot functions (diet matrix, mortality, etc.) will be released soon.

Fig. 7.4: Biomass plot

Fig. 7.5: Abundance plot

Fig. 7.6: Yield biomass plot

Fig. 7.7: Yield abundance plot

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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- [And19] Ken H. Andersen. *Fish Ecology, Evolution, and Exploitation: A New Theoretical Synthesis*. Monographs in Population Biology, 2019.
- [AJA09] Michael J Angilletta Jr and Michael James Angilletta. *Thermal adaptation: a theoretical and empirical synthesis*. Oxford University Press, 2009.
- [APH+16] Vickery L Arcus, Erica J Prentice, Joanne K Hobbs, Adrian J Mulholland, Marc W Van der Kamp, Christopher R Pudney, Emily J Parker, and Louis A Schipper. On the temperature dependence of enzyme-catalyzed rates. *Biochemistry*, 55(12):1681–1688, 2016.
- [BDE+14] David S Boukal, Ulf Dieckmann, Katja Enberg, Mikko Heino, and Christian Jørgensen. Life-history implications of the allometric scaling of growth. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 359:199–207, 2014.
- [BGA+04] James H Brown, James F Gillooly, Andrew P Allen, Van M Savage, and Geoffrey B West. Toward a metabolic theory of ecology. *Ecology*, 85(7):1771–1789, 2004.
- [CTW01] Eric L Charnov, Thomas F Turner, and Kirk O Winemiller. Reproductive constraints and the evolution of life histories with indeterminate growth. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 98(16):9460–9464, 2001.
- [CW04] Villy Christensen and Carl J Walters. Ecopath with ecosim: methods, capabilities and limitations. *Ecological modelling*, 172(2-4):109–139, 2004.
- [Cla17] Andrew Clarke. *Principles of thermal ecology: Temperature, energy and life*. Oxford University Press, 2017.
- [Cla19] Andrew Clarke. Energy flow in growth and production. *Trends in ecology & evolution*, 34(6):502–509, 2019.
- [DFS+15] Curtis Deutsch, Aaron Ferrel, Brad Seibel, Hans-Otto Pörtner, and Raymond B Huey. Climate change tightens a metabolic constraint on marine habitats. *Science*, 348(6239):1132–1135, 2015.
- [DPS20] Curtis Deutsch, Justin L Penn, and Brad Seibel. Metabolic trait diversity shapes marine biogeography. *Nature*, 585(7826):557–562, 2020.
- [FOT+17] Caihong Fu, Norm Olsen, Nathan Taylor, Arnaud Grüss, Sonia Batten, Huizhu Liu, Philippe Verley, and Yunne-Jai Shin. Spatial and temporal dynamics of predator-prey species interactions off western Canada. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 74(8):2107–2119, 05 2017. doi:10.1093/icesjms/fsx056.
- [FPS+13] Caihong Fu, R Ian Perry, Yunne-Jai Shin, Jake Schweigert, and Huizhu Liu. An ecosystem modelling framework for incorporating climate regime shifts into fisheries management. *Progress in oceanography*, 115:53–64, 2013. doi:10.1016/j.pocean.2013.03.003.
- [GCW+02] James F Gillooly, Eric L Charnov, Geoffrey B West, Van M Savage, and James H Brown. Effects of size and temperature on developmental time. *Nature*, 417(6884):70–73, 2002.

- [GBB+06] Volker Grimm, Uta Berger, Finn Bastiansen, Sigrunn Eliassen, Vincent Ginot, Jarl Giske, John Goss-Custard, Tamara Grand, Simone K. Heinz, Geir Huse, Andreas Huth, Jane U. Jepsen, Christian Jørgensen, Wolf M. Mooij, Birgit Müller, Guy Pe'er, Cyril Piou, Steven F. Railsback, Andrew M. Robbins, Martha M. Robbins, Eva Rossmanith, Nadja Rüger, Espen Strand, Sami Souissi, Richard A. Stillman, Rune Vabø, Ute Visser, and Donald L. DeAngelis. A standard protocol for describing individual-based and agent-based models. *Ecological Modelling*, 198(1):115–126, 2006. doi:10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2006.04.023.
- [GBD+10] Volker Grimm, Uta Berger, Donald L. DeAngelis, J. Gary Polhill, Jarl Giske, and Steven F. Railsback. The odd protocol: a review and first update. *Ecological Modelling*, 221(23):2760–2768, 2010. doi:10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2010.08.019.
- [GRV+20] Volker Grimm, Steven F. Railsback, Christian E. Vincenot, Uta Berger, Cara Gallagher, Donald L. DeAngelis, Bruce Edmonds, Jiaqi Ge, Jarl Giske, Jürgen Groeneveld, Alice S.A. Johnston, Alexander Milles, Jacob Nabe-Nielsen, Gary Polhill, Viktoriia Radchuk, Marie-Sophie Rohwäder, Richard A. Stillman, Jan C. Thiele, and Daniel Ayllón. The odd protocol for describing agent-based and other simulation models: a second update to improve clarity, replication, and structural realism. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 23(2):7, 2020. doi:10.18564/jasss.4259.
- [GQ16] Rolf A. Groeneveld and Martin F. Quaas. Promoting selective fisheries through certification? an analysis of the PNA unassociated-sets purse seine fishery. *Fisheries Research*, 182:69 – 78, 2016. doi:10.1016/j.fishres.2015.10.014.
- [GrussSC+15] Arnaud Grüss, Michael J Schirripa, David Chagaris, Michael Drexler, James Simons, Philippe Verley, Yunne-Jai Shin, Mandy Karnauskas, Ricardo Oliveros-Ramos, and Cameron H Ainsworth. Evaluation of the trophic structure of the west florida shelf in the 2000s using the ecosystem model osmose. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 144:30–47, 2015. doi:10.1016/j.jmarsys.2014.11.004.
- [HLS+16] Ghassen Halouani, Frida Ben Rais Lasram, Yunne-Jai Shin, Laure Velez, Philippe Verley, Tarek Hattab, Ricardo Oliveros-Ramos, Frédéric Diaz, Frédéric Ménard, Melika Baklouti, Arnaud Guyennon, Mohamed Salah Romdhane, and François Le Loch. Modelling food web structure using an end-to-end approach in the coastal ecosystem of the gulf of gabes (tunisia). *Ecological Modelling*, 339(Supplement C):45–57, 2016. doi:10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2016.08.008.
- [HDGodo02] Mikko Heino, Ulf Dieckmann, and Olav Rune Godø. Measuring probabilistic reaction norms for age and size at maturation. *Evolution*, 56(4):669–678, 2002.
- [HDiazPD15] Mikko Heino, Beatriz Díaz Pauli, and Ulf Dieckmann. Fisheries-induced evolution. *Annual review of ecology, evolution, and systematics*, 46:461–480, 2015.
- [Hol59] Crawford S Holling. The components of predation as revealed by a study of small-mammal predation of the european pine sawfly1. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 91(5):293–320, 1959.
- [HJorgensen14] Rebecca E Holt and Christian Jørgensen. Climate warming causes life-history evolution in a model for atlantic cod (gadus morhua). *Conservation Physiology*, 2(1):cou050, 2014.
- [JL46] Frank H. Johnson and Isaac Lewin. The growth rate of e. coli in relation to temperature, quinine and coenzyme. *Journal of Cellular and Comparative Physiology*, 28(1):47–75, 1946. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/jcp.1030280104>, arXiv:<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/jcp.1030280104>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/jcp.1030280104>.
- [Koo09] Bas Kooijman. *Dynamic Energy Budget Theory for Metabolic Organisation*. Cambridge University Press, 3 edition, 2009. doi:10.1017/CBO9780511805400.
- [LDDS19] Kira Lancker, A.L. Deppenmeier, T. Demissie, and J.O. Schmidt. Climate change adaptation and the role of fuel subsidies: an empirical bio-economic modeling study for an artisanal open-access fishery. *PLoS ONE*, 14(8):e0220433, 2019. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0220433.

- [LMN17] Sjannie Lefevre, David J McKenzie, and Göran E Nilsson. Models projecting the fate of fish populations under climate change need to be based on valid physiological mechanisms. *Global Change Biology*, 23(9):3449–3459, 2017.
- [LMN18] Sjannie Lefevre, David J McKenzie, and Göran E Nilsson. In modelling effects of global warming, invalid assumptions lead to unrealistic projections. *Global change biology*, 24(2):553–556, 2018.
- [LSA04] NP Lester, BJ Shuter, and PA Abrams. Interpreting the von bertalanffy model of somatic growth in fishes: the cost of reproduction. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences*, 271(1548):1625–1631, 2004.
- [LW+98] Michael Lynch, Bruce Walsh, and others. *Genetics and analysis of quantitative traits*. Volume 1. Sinauer Sunderland, MA, 1998.
- [Man03] Marc Mangel. Environment and longevity: the demography of the growth rate. *Population and Development Review*, 29:57–70, 2003.
- [MEBR10] Fabian M Mollet, Bruno Ernande, Thomas Brunel, and Adriaan D Rijnsdorp. Multiple growth-correlated life history traits estimated simultaneously in individuals. *Oikos*, 119(1):10–26, 2010.
- [OR14] Ricardo Oliveros Ramos. *End-to-end modelling for an ecosystem approach to fisheries in the Northern Humboldt Current Ecosystem*. PhD thesis, University of Montpellier, France, 2014.
- [ORS17] Ricardo Oliveros-Ramos and Yunne-Jai Shin. Calibrar: an r package for fitting complex ecological models. ???, ???:???, ??? 2017.
- [ORVES17] Ricardo Oliveros-Ramos, Philippe Verley, Vincent Echevin, and Yunne-Jai Shin. A sequential approach to calibrate ecosystem models with multiple time series data. *PROGRESS IN OCEANOGRAPHY*, 151:227–244, FEB 2017. doi:10.1016/j.pocean.2017.01.002.
- [PDS15] Samraat Pawar, Anthony I Dell, and Van M Savage. From metabolic constraints on individuals to the dynamics of ecosystems. In *Aquatic functional biodiversity*, pages 3–36. Elsevier, 2015.
- [Portner01] H Pörtner. Climate change and temperature-dependent biogeography: oxygen limitation of thermal tolerance in animals. *Naturwissenschaften*, 88:137–146, 2001.
- [QR13] Martin F. Quaas and Till Requate. Sushi or fish fingers? seafood diversity, collapsing fish stocks and multi-species fishery management. *Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 115(2):381–422, 2013. doi:10.1111/sjoe.12002.
- [QRS+16] Martin F. Quaas, Thorsten B. H. Reusch, Jörn O. Schmidt, Olli Tahvonen, and Rudi Voss. It is the economy, stupid! projecting the fate of fish populations using ecological-economic modeling. *Global Change Biology*, 22(1):264–270, 2016. doi:10.1111/gcb.13060.
- [QSK+18] Martin F. Quaas, Max T. Stoeven, Bernd Klauer, Thomas Petersen, and Johannes Schiller. Windows of opportunity for sustainable fisheries management: the case of Eastern Baltic cod. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 70(2):323–341, 2018. doi:10.1007/s10640-017-0122-y.
- [QASL08] Christopher Quince, Peter A Abrams, Brian J Shuter, and Nigel P Lester. Biphasic growth in fish i: theoretical foundations. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 254(2):197–206, 2008.
- [Rof22] Derek Roff. *The evolution of life histories: theory and analysis*. New York: Chapman and Hall, 1922.
- [SBD+95] M. Scheffer, J.M. Baveco, D.L. DeAngelis, K.A. Rose, and E.H. van Nes. Super-individuals a simple solution for modelling large populations on an individual basis. *Ecological Modelling*, 80(2):161–170, 1995. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3800(94)00055-M.
- [SMJF03] Lynne J Shannon, Coleen L Moloney, Astrid Jarre, and John G Field. Trophic flows in the southern benguela during the 1980s and 1990s. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 39(1):83–116, 2003. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-7963(02)00250-6.

- [SC01] YJ Shin and P Cury. Exploring fish community dynamics through size-dependent trophic interactions using a spatialized individual-based model. *AQUATIC LIVING RESOURCES*, 14(2):65–80, MAR-APR 2001. doi:10.1016/S0990-7440(01)01106-8.
- [SC04] YJ Shin and P Cury. Using an individual-based model of fish assemblages to study the response of size spectra to changes in fishing. *CANADIAN JOURNAL OF FISHERIES AND AQUATIC SCIENCES*, 61(3):414–431, MAR 2004. doi:10.1139/F03-154.
- [SK12] Jean-Paul Soularue and Antoine Kremer. Assortative mating and gene flow generate clinal phenological variation in trees. *BMC evolutionary biology*, 12(1):1–14, 2012.
- [Ste92] Stephen C Stearns. *The evolution of life histories*. Volume 249. Oxford university press Oxford, 1992.
- [SK86] Stephen C Stearns and Jacob C Koella. The evolution of phenotypic plasticity in life-history traits: predictions of reaction norms for age and size at maturity. *Evolution*, 40(5):893–913, 1986.
- [TQV18] Olli Tahvonen, Martin F. Quaas, and Rüdiger Voss. Harvesting selectivity and stochastic recruitment in economic models of age-structured fisheries. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 92:659–676, 2018. doi:10.1016/j.jeem.2017.08.011.
- [TFSMC+19] Yoann Thomas, Jonathan Flye-Sainte-Marie, Denis Chabot, Arturo Aguirre-Velarde, Gonçalo M. Marques, and Laure Pecquerie. Effects of hypoxia on metabolic functions in marine organisms: observed patterns and modelling assumptions within the context of dynamic energy budget (deb) theory. *Journal of Sea Research*, 143:231–242, 2019. Ecosystem based management and the biosphere: a new phase in DEB research. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1385110118300315>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2018.05.001>.
- [TPRM17] BL Townhill, JK Pinnegar, DA Righton, and JD Metcalfe. Fisheries, low oxygen and climate change: how much do we really know? *Journal of Fish Biology*, 90(3):723–750, 2017.
- [TSSC06] M Travers, YJ Shin, L Shannon, and P Cury. Simulating and testing the sensitivity of ecosystem-based indicators to fishing in the southern benguela ecosystem. *CANADIAN JOURNAL OF FISHERIES AND AQUATIC SCIENCES*, 63(4):943–956, APR 2006. doi:10.1139/1706-003.
- [TSJ+09] M. Travers, Y.-J. Shin, S. Jennings, E. Machu, J.A. Huggett, J.G. Field, and P.M. Cury. Two-way coupling versus one-way forcing of plankton and fish models to predict ecosystem changes in the benguela. *Ecological Modelling*, 220("21):3089 – 3099, 2009. Selected Papers from the Sixth European Conference on Ecological Modelling - ECEM '07, on Challenges for ecological modelling in a changing world: Global Changes, Sustainability and Ecosystem Based Management, November 27-30, 2007, Trieste, Italy. doi:10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2009.08.016.
- [TTSF14] M Travers-Trolet, Y-J Shin, and JG Field. An end-to-end coupled model roms-n2p2z2d2-osmose of the southern benguela foodweb: parameterisation, calibration and pattern-oriented validation. *African Journal of Marine Science*, 36(1):11–29, 2014. URL: [10.2989/1814232X.2014.883326](https://doi.org/10.2989/1814232X.2014.883326), arXiv:10.2989/1814232X.2014.883326, doi:10.2989/1814232X.2014.883326.

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